

SATISFACTORY

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BPEL	Business Process Execution Language
BPM	Business Process Modelling
CB	Collaboration Broker
CIDEM	Common Information Data Exchange Model
CMMS	Computerised Maintenance Management System
DAC	Device Application Catalogue
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DM	Device Manager
DoW	Description of Work
DSM	Demand Side Management
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
EU	European Union
FoFPPP	Factory of the Future Public-Private Partnership
GW	Gateway

HMI	Human Machine Interface
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LEAP	Linked Engineering and Manufacturing Platform
M2M	Machine to Machine
MES	Manufacturing Execution System
MTBF	Mean Time Between Failures
MTTR	Mean Time To Failure
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OSF	Open Semantic Framework
OSGi DA	OSGi Device Abstraction Layer
P2P	Peer to Peer
PC	Personal Computer
PWAL	Physical World Adaptation Layer
QoS	Quality of Service
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SCM	Supply Chain Management
SFP	SatisFactory Platform
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SOA	Service-Oriented Architecture
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol

SSN	Smart Sensor Network
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modelling Language
UWB	Ultra Wide Band
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
WSAN	Wireless Sensor and Actuator Networks
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes a first version of the SatisFactory architecture. There will be an updated version of the architecture description due at M16 and a final one at M27.

The first part of the document presents the methodology used to achieve and document the architecture that has been defined as a result of three main steps namely, *technology exploration*, *bottom-up* and *top-down*. In the technology exploration phase both relevant EU funded projects and regional ones have been analysed in order to identify critical aspects for the SatisFactory architecture that should be taken into account. In the *bottom-up* phase, technology partners have described in detail their main components and their expertise requested by SatisFactory, after that on the basis of the requirements from Task 1.1 a first version of the SatisFactory architecture has been defined. In the *top-down* phase, applications and platform services have been preliminary tested by means of UML sequence diagrams by taking as input uses cases defined within Task 1.3. The documentation of the architecture has been based on the standard IEEE 1471 "Recommended Practice for Architectural Description for Software-Intensive Systems" [IEEE 1471, 2000]. It implies a process based on a set of relevant architecture viewpoints. For SatisFactory three functional viewpoints have been defined, namely *functional view*, *deployment view* and *information view*.

In the *functional view* the components, their functionality, and their interactions are described. The main identified architecture components are:

- Smart Sensor Network, which includes sensors, wearable devices as well as a Dependable Network Infrastructure providing robust communication and correct data delivery in harsh radio propagation environments.
- Decision Support System (DSS) component, which provides decision on the basis of feedback coming from the shop floor, changes to manufacturing operations and processes, as well as maintenance operations and schedules.
- Safety related modules, such as Gesture & Content Recognition, Multi-Media, Localization, and Semantic Context Manager.
- Satisfaction and training related components, such as Collaborative Tools, Augmented Reality (AR)-In Factory and the Training Education Platforms.
- Finally, a visualization layer has been foreseen, which includes AR-Glasses User Interface (UI), Visual Analytics Module and adaptable Smartphone/Tablet UIs.

The *deployment view* describes how and where the system will be deployed, which physical components are needed, what are the dependencies, hardware requirements and physical constraints. The *information view* describes the application domain models and the data flow as well as the distribution.

Finally, a number of use cases have been described through sequence diagrams. The purpose of these sequence diagrams is to clarify how the SatisFactory platform will work and which components are relevant to achieve different tasks.

1. INTRODUCTION

This section outlines the purpose, background, and context of this deliverable as well as the structure of the remaining document.

1.1 *PURPOSE, CONTEXT AND SCOPE OF THIS DELIVERABLE*

This deliverable defines the initial architecture for the SatisFactory platform. It is worth remarking that the requirements for the architecture can change during the course of the project while some aspects of the architecture need verification during development, and therefore the architecture described here cannot be considered to be final or complete. There will be an updated version of the architecture description at M16, and a final version due at M27.

Within the SatisFactory work package (WP) structure, Task 2.1 (Reference Architecture Design and Technology Exploration) is responsible for analysing the relevant state of the art as well as specifying the SatisFactory system architecture. Having completed the previous steps in WP1 (Domain Analysis and Requirements Engineering), providing an initial set of requirements, this deliverable defines the system architecture, preparing for prototypal implementation to be carried out by the technical work packages within WP3 and WP4.

The architectural description includes aspects related to the identification of the major system components, how they should interact and how their external interfaces should be defined.

This document is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the methodology for defining and documenting the architecture. Section 3 presents an analysis of technologies and relevant SatisFactory projects. Sections from 4 to 8 contain the different views of the architecture, namely functional view, information view and deployment view; these are then instantiated for specific technical use cases in section 9. The document also possesses two annexes: Annex 1 reports in detail the analysis of the relevant SatisFactory projects while Annex 2 presents the description of all subcomponents brought by partners that have been used to support the architecture definition process.

1.2 *BACKGROUND*

The SatisFactory Platform (SFP) aims to make traditional factories more attractive, supported by continuous training of their employees, by stimulating team interactions and capitalising the created knowledge and experience in every level of their organization. Going into details, the SFP collects, aggregates and analyses real-time data from heterogeneous sensors, privacy preserving infrared and depth cameras deployed in the shop floor, interact with Augmented Reality (AR) glasses and novel HMIs through a fundamental component that is the Middleware. In order to distribute the gathered knowledge efficiently and improve the well-being of both the employees and organisation, three main tools are considered, namely, an integrated DSS, a real-time training environment and finally an independent, pervasive data communication network. Additionally, the

SFP addresses workers' safety through proper context aware modules, monitors the production facilities for detecting flaws and problems, and triggers re-adaptation as means for rectifying anomalies and improving throughput. Finally, in order to present all the above information and control capabilities, intuitive and easy to use interfaces, among them AR environments are used. Gamification methods are applied for motivating workers for unpopular tasks. The SFP will be demonstrated in three different pilots belonging to the three end users (i.e., COMAU, SUNLIGHT, CERTH), where each one targets at different aspect of the operation and activities.

2. ARCHITECTURE DESIGN APPROACH & METHODOLOGY

This section presents the approach and methodology that have been followed by Task 2.1 to define the first version of the architecture. It is reminded that Task 2.1 uses the following three temporal iterations M₃-M₈, M₁₅-M₁₆ and M₂₇-M₂₈. The first iteration defines the first version of the architecture while the other two iterations are used to further improve the architecture on the basis of inputs coming from the following technical work packages WP₃, WP₄ and WP₅.

In this first iteration, the architecture definition process has involved three main phases (*technology exploration*, *bottom-up* and *top-down*) as depicted in Figure 1. As it can be observed, the process takes two main inputs from WP1: technical requirements reported in D1.1 [SatisFactory D1.1] (available at M₄) and use cases (UCs) reported in D1.2 [SatisFactory D1.2] (available at M₇). In the *technology exploration* phase, relevant research projects and adopted solutions have been analysed in order identify critical aspects of the SatisFactory architecture that should be taken into account. In the *bottom-up* phase, the initiation of the architecture definition process has been carried out based on technologies and software modules brought by partners that have been considered necessary for the SatisFactory platform. Additionally, the architecture has been built based on the LinkSmart Middleware, which has also guided us with its pre-existent structure. Finally, the *top-down* phase is driven by the use cases that have been used to test the role and interaction among the main components.

Figure 1. Architecture Design Methodology (First Iteration).

Later this section presents in more detail the last two phases. In particular, section 2.1 presents the *bottom-up* process that shows how we have gathered and combined individual technologies and components that the partners brought into the project; additionally, on the basis of the technical requirements presented in D1.1 [SatisFactory D1.1] we have also identified missing modules and functionalities that are foreseen by the SatisFactory and that will be developed and integrated along the project. As a result, this phase produced more detailed views on the initial SatisFactory conceptual architecture, which has been presented in the DoW (see Figure 2). Section 2.2 afterwards deals with the *top-down* process. This phase has been driven by UCs presented in D1.2

[SatisFactory D1.2]. During these two phases we have held three workshops that lead us step by step toward the definition of the architecture that is presented in this deliverable.

Figure 2. Initial SatisFactory Conceptual Architecture as Presented in the DoW.

2.1 BOTTOM-UP PROCESS

This phase (M₄-M₆) has aimed to collect and categorize the technologies and software components that the individual partners of the SatisFactory project brought in with them. In addition, partners' expertise have been quickly identified and used as best as possible in this first process. This has also helped us to identify gaps in the architecture that needed to be filled to achieve the platform envisioned by the SatisFactory project.

As first step of this phase, a template has been defined in order to collect a short description of all components and sub-components brought by the partners. In particular, this template has aimed to collect the following component information: description of the main functionalities, related services, dependencies, inputs needed and outputs provided.

Altogether 11 main components have been identified. Some of them also included sub-components, in total 38. The full list of components and subcomponents along with associated responsibilities is reported in Figure 3.

Main component	Sub-component	Responsible partner	Contributing partners
Smart Sensor Network		ISMB	CERTH, COMAU, SUNLIGHT
	Dependable Network Infrastructure	ISMB	
	UWB Localization Devices	ISMB	
	Depth Sensor Network	CERTH	
	Thermal Sensor Network	CERTH	
	Automation Systems - I/O Field Network	COMAU, SUNLIGHT, CERTH/CPERI	
Middleware		FIT	ISMB, CERTH
	Middleware-Core	FIT	
	Device Manager	ISMB	CERTH, FIT
	Event Manager	FIT	
Semantic Context Manager		EPFL	CERTH, ISMB
	Ontology Manager	EPFL	
	Localization Manager	ISMB	CERTH, EPFL
	Multi-Media Manager	ISMB	CERTH, EPFL
	Gesture & Content Recognition Manager	ISMB	CERTH, EPFL
Collaborative Tools		FIT	REGOLA
	Social Interaction and Cooperation (Applications)	FIT	REGOLA
	Gamified Process Support	FIT	
Integrated DSS		ABE	COMAU, CERTH, ISMB
	DSS-Core	ABE	
	Operation Procedures	COMAU	ABE
	Maintenance Procedures	ABE	CERTH
	Shopfloor Feedback Engine	ABE	
	Incident Management Tools	CERTH	ISMB, ABE
	Maintenance Toolkit	ABE	
	Production Activities Tools	CERTH	ABE
	Real-time Analytics	CERTH	ABE
	Visual Analytics Module	CERTH	
AR In-Factory Platform		REGOLA	CERTH
	Gamification Augmented Reality	REGOLA	CERTH
	SOP & Content Data Enrichment Tools	REGOLA	
	AR SOP Creation Tools	REGOLA	
	AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job	REGOLA	
	AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework	REGOLA	
Repository		CERTH	ABE
	Incident-related Dynamic & Persistent Data	CERTH	
	Asset-Machinery-Production Data	CERTH	ABE
	Asset-Machinery-Production Models	ABE	CERTH
Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence		CERTH	ABE, REGOLA
	None		
Training Educational Platform		REGOLA	ABE
	On the job training & education Sw module	REGOLA	CERTH, ABE
	Training in Manufacturing Procedures for Maintenance a	ABE	
Readaptation Toolkit		ISMB	ISMB
	None		
Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices		GlassUP	FIT
	Adaptable user interfaces and interaction techniques	FIT	
	AR Glasses	GlassUP	
	HMIs	REGOLA	

Figure 3. List of Identified Components and Sub-components and Partners Responsibilities.

For each subcomponent a description has been provided according to the provided template by the responsible partner. All the collected sub-component descriptions can be found in Annex 2. As next step, we have started putting the components into an initial architecture, identified services and dependencies within the platform. We have also added new components in order to cover all the required SatisFactory functionalities.

The result of this process is presented in section 4.1, which includes the defined overall SatisFactory functional architecture. As it can be observed from Figure 4, the SatisFactory overall architecture has been subdivided in different layers, as specified initially, where components are of different nature and offer different functionalities. Having identified this issue, we have clarified the role of each layer in section 4.1.

2.2 *TOP-DOWN PROCESS*

This phase (M7-M8) has been strongly focused on each component's role and their interaction. To this purpose, we have taken advantage of the use cases identified within Task 1.3 and reported in D1.2 [SatisFactory D1.2], and build the related sequence diagrams by considering the components already identified. This has allowed us to stress the services each component would provide, and sketch the interactions between them. Using this approach, and taking into consideration functionalities to be provided, we have also refined and discussed high level components APIs.

2.3 *ARCHITECTURE DESIGN WORKSHOPS*

Along the bottom-up and top-down processes, three online architecture design workshops have been organized, involving technical as well as end-user partners, in order to iteratively define the overall SatisFactory architecture and all its views. In the following sections we summarize these three workshops.

2.3.1 *Architecture Design Workshop One*

Date: May 12th, 2015.

In the first workshop, which was held during the bottom-up process, we reviewed all the components and sub-components brought by the partners. In addition, we identified missing components and technologies on the basis of technical requirements identified within WP1 and reported in D1.1 [SatisFactory D1.1] as well as taking into consideration all the SatisFactory functionalities reported in the DoW. After that, going to the direction of the first definition of the overall architecture, partners responsible of main components have been asked to provide the related internal architecture also showing the interaction with the other SatisFactory main components.

2.3.2 *Architecture Design Workshop Two*

Date: June 17th, 2015.

During the second workshop, which was held during the bottom-up process, the first version of the overall SatisFactory architecture was presented and discussed with the aim to further refine it. First of all, during this workshop, the capability of the LinkSmart Middleware component was highlighted, that is able to incorporate heterogeneous physical devices into applications by offering easy-to-use web service interfaces irrespective of devices' network technology. After that, it was remarked that the communication among the SatisFactory components can be enabled by means of the "Event Manager" sub-component, which belongs to the Middleware. Doing so, it was observed that scalability issues may arise if all components use the Event Manager for their interaction. As an alternative, it has been proposed to use a hybrid approach, where some components use the Middleware (i.e. the Event Manager sub-component) to exchange data and/or to signal any types of events, whereas others use a direct communication, by means of ad-hoc APIs, to exchange big amount of data, such as video streams.

2.3.3 *Architecture Design Workshop Three*

Date: July 09th, 2015.

The top-down process has been initiated by the third workshop within which we also started the discussion about the definition of the deployment and information views of the architecture. As mentioned above, the top-down process has taken as main input the use cases identified within Task 1.3, which have been reported in D1.2 [SatisFactory D1.2]. Among the 21 identified UCs, only 10 have been selected to be analysed by means of sequence diagrams. The UCs selection has been performed such that the main components of SatisFactory appear in at least one sequence diagram. It has been agreed with the whole consortium to draw the sequence diagrams regarding the remaining UCs during the next iteration of the SatisFactory architecture, i.e. between M13 and M14.

2.4 *DOCUMENTATION OF THE ARCHITECTURE*

The process used for documenting the architecture in this deliverable is based on the standard IEEE 1471 "Recommended Practice for Architectural Description for Software-Intensive Systems" [IEEE 1471, 2000]. This standard establishes a methodology for the architectural description of software intensive systems. One main part of this methodology is the use of viewpoints: collections of patterns, templates and conventions for constructing one type of view. One example is the functional viewpoint, which contains all functions that the system should perform, the responsibilities and interfaces of the functional elements and the relationship between them. These functions can be described using UML diagrams. In this initial version of the architecture, we have decided to define the three most important viewpoints: functional, information and deployment viewpoints.

- Functional viewpoint (section 4): This viewpoint describes the functional elements needed to meet the key requirements of the architecture. It will present proposals in a descriptive way and UML component diagrams will assist in the understanding of the proposal. It will describe responsibilities, interfaces, and interactions between the functional elements.
- Deployment viewpoint (section 6): This viewpoint describes how and where the system will be deployed and what dependencies exist, considering for example hardware requirements and physical restraints.
- Information viewpoint (section 7): The information viewpoint describes the data models and the data flow as well as the distribution. The viewpoint also defines which data will be stored and where. The description of where data will be manipulated is also a part of this viewpoint.

Finally, to address quality properties and cross-cutting concerns, architectural perspectives are presented as well in section 8. Typical examples for SatisFactory are: satisfaction (section 8.1), safety (section 8.2) and scalability (section 8.3) perspectives.

3. TECHNOLOGY EXPLORATION

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this section is to explore the appropriate technologies that are relevant to SatisFactory and use these results as input for the architecture definition process. Moreover, critical architectural aspects are identified that should be taken into account during the architecture definition. In particular, this section presents a H2020 project funded under the same call FoFo4 and other relevant FP7 funded projects and regional ones, where members of the SatisFactory consortium had been involved in.

Table 1 provides a higher level overview of the selected relevant projects with information such as research area, duration of the project, and partners involved with their core role in the project in the context of SatisFactory project.

A more detailed analysis of the relevant research projects is reported in the Annex 1.

Table 1. Selected SatisFactory Relevant Projects for the Technology Exploration.

Name of Project	Project Information	Involved Partner
FACTS₄WORKERS (Worker-Centric Workplaces in Smart Factories)	<p>Research area: Developing smart factories that are attractive to workers</p> <p>Tech. Area: H2020-FoF4</p> <p>Duration: Start: 1.12.2014 – 48 months</p> <p>Website: http://facts4workers.eu/</p>	None from SatisFactory
mainDSS (maintenance Decision Support System)	<p>Research area: Eurostars Project (international research for R&D intensive SMEs)</p> <p>Tech. Area: 1.2.15 Knowledge Management, Process Management</p> <p>Market Area: 8.7 Industrial Services</p> <p>Duration: Start: 7/2010 – 40 months</p> <p>Role of Partner: Coordinator / Main Technical Contributor</p> <p>Website: www.maindss.eu</p>	ABE
LinkedDesign	<p>Research area: FP7-2011-NMP-ICT-FoF</p> <p>Tech. Area: FoF-ICT-2011.7.4 - Digital factories</p> <p>Market Area: Manufacturing design and product lifecycle management</p> <p>Call: Duration: Start: 09/2011 – 48 months</p> <p>Role of Partner: EPFL was the leader of Ontology and</p>	EPFL

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	<p>Inference system for design and manufacturing domain work package. EPFL contributed to the overall architecture and requirements, as well as to the standardization efforts.</p> <p>Website: www.linkeddesign.eu/</p>	
PlantCockpit	<p>Research area: EU FP7 FoF ICT 2010</p> <p>Call: Duration: Start: 09/2010 – 39 months</p> <p>Role of Partner: EPFL was the leader of Requirements and Standardization work packages. EPFL was also involved in Data and Process modelling. EPFL contributed to the overall architecture and KPI interdependences concept and reference model</p> <p>Website: http://plantcockpit.eu/</p>	EPFL
CoSpaces (Innovative collaborative work environments for engineering and design)	<p>Research Area: Collaborative Working Environments</p> <p>Call: IST-2005-2.5.9</p> <p>Duration: Start: 5/2006 – 42 months</p> <p>Role of Partner: FIT was responsible for knowledge distribution and group management in combination with mobile and augmented reality systems.</p> <p>Website: http://www.cospaces.org/</p>	FIT
Mirror (Mirror - Reflective Learning at Work)	<p>Research Area: Technology-enhanced learning</p> <p>Call: ICT-2009.4.2</p> <p>Duration: 2010-07 – 48 months</p> <p>Role of Partner: Application Partner. The application case will be in the Civil Protection Organisation in Turin (Torino).</p> <p>Website: http://www.mirror-project.eu/</p>	Regola
Adapt4EE (Occupant Aware, Intelligent, Adaptive Enterprises)	<p>Project name: Adapt4EE</p> <p>Research area: ICT systems for energy efficiency (FP7-ICT-2011-6.2)</p> <p>Duration: 11/2011 – 36 months</p> <p>Role of Partner: CERTH was the coordinator of the project. Furthermore, the occupancy extraction and modelling components and the occupancy simulation engine implemented within this project have been designed and developed by CERTH, while the middleware module and its sub-components have been implemented by Fraunhofer.</p> <p>Website: http://www.adapt4ee.eu/</p>	CERTH

INERTIA (Integrating Active, Flexible and Responsive Tertiary Prosumers into a Smart Distribution Grid)	Research area: ICT systems for energy efficiency (FP7-ICT-2011-8) Duration: 10/2012 - 36 months Role of Partner: CERTH was the coordinator of the project and has designed and developed the occupancy extraction, modelling and prediction component implemented within this project. Website: http://www.inertia-project.eu/	CERTH
ebbits (enabling the business-based internet of things and services)	Research area: ICT-2009.1.3 - Internet of Things and Enterprise environments Call: FP7-ICT-2009-5 Duration: 9/2010 –53 months Role of Partner: Leader of WP8 – Physical World Sensors and Networks Website: http://www.ebbits-project.eu/	ISMB, FIT

3.2 ANALYSIS

Critical architectural aspects of the selected relevant projects and their technical advantages in the context of SatisFactory are briefly described as follows.

- *FACTS4WORKERS* [Facts4Workers] uses the information and communication technology to improve manufacturing process regarding flexibility, efficiency, reliability; further, this essential information is supported by optimized information and communication technology, self-learning working environment, and in-situ learning for the workers while operating the machines.
- *mainDSS* [mainDSS] project tries to maximize the operational availability of assets and minimize the life-cycle costs in order to improve the competitive business environment by improving the maintenance departments and decisions; thus, an effective communication between managerial and technical departments is established by prioritizing the necessary maintenance pillars. In SatisFactory an improved shop floor feedback and decision making system will be provided for gains in productivity, workers wellbeing and comfort. Also it will reuse the maintenance and production facilities ontology, the decision support engine, as well as the algorithms for producing recommendations for improving intra-factory procedures and maintenance operations developed in the previous project.
- *LinkedDesign* [LinkedDesign] project decouples the actual process execution from the design and engineering of products, and the manufacturing processes. The project provides a solution that allows the integration of the holistic view on data across the full product lifecycle for ICT by developing methodologies and novel integration tools. SatisFactory is going to use the framework developed before as a basis for context-aware services, most

importantly for the acquisition of context information and its presentation in a way that can be properly interpreted and managed.

- PlantCockpit [PlantCockPit] project develops a central environment for monitoring and controlling of all intra-logistical processes within a manufacturing environment. PLANTCockpit provides production supervisors, foremen, and line managers with the required visibility to make well-informed decisions for optimizing plant processes in a quick and efficient way. SatisFactory will use the plant visualization outcome of PlantCockpit and enrich it with a semantic framework which will support the context-aware platform for an improved shop floor environment.
- CoSpaces [CoSpaces] project uses technologies in manufacturing and design for groundbreaking innovations in context-aware interfaces, natural interfaces, and “human-centric” workspaces supporting a range of collaboration scenarios within product lifecycles. The developed platform supports product design and manufacturing in geographically dispersed teams in distributed virtual engineering enterprises. It helps the team members to participate in decision-making, view designs, propose modifications, and access reference material in ways that are specific to their disciplines, and allows them to interact using a range of devices depending on their current location and situation. In SatisFactory, the platform will be enhanced by social networking and gamification aspects.
- The vision of *MIRROR* is to empower and motivate employees to learn by reflection of tacit work practices and personal experiences. MIRROR shall help employees capture experiences and collaboratively develop creative solutions for problems that need to be solved immediately [Mirror 2015]. This will be achieved by complementing personal and organisational learning environments (which mainly rely on knowledge being explicitly available) with highly personal MIRROR applications for individual, social, creative, game-based as well as organisational reflection and real-time learning.
- Adapt4EE aims at augmenting the contemporary architectural envelope by incorporating business and occupancy related information thus providing a holistic approach to the planning, design & evaluation of energy performance of construction products at an early design phase [Adapt4EE]. Adapt4EE aims to deliver and validate a holistic energy performance framework that incorporates architectural metadata and environmental parameters (i.e., BIM), critical business models (i.e., BPM), treating occupants as the central reference point [Adapt4EE]. The new device managers for occupancy already implemented will be transferred to SatisFactory as valuable input for the extensions needed in the project.
- INERTIA [Jimeno et al.] project aims at providing an overlay network for coordination and active grid control, running on top of the existing grid and consisting of distributed and autonomous intelligent Commercial Prosumer Hubs. This way, it will address the present “structural inertia” of DG by introducing more active elements combined with the necessary control and distributed coordination mechanisms.
- The ebbits project² provides semantic approach to IoT and hence introduces an innovative bridge between backend enterprise applications, people, services and the physical world, using information generated by tags, sensors, and other devices and performing actions on the real world. The ebbits platform is based on SoA (Service Oriented Architecture), so virtualizing every device into a service and allowing these services to semantically discover,

² www.ebbits-project.eu

configure, and communicate with each other. Furthermore, the ebbits platform aims at supporting interoperable applications to process context-aware data, separated in time and space, acquiring information and real-world events and to handle end-to-end business workflows, including comprehensive consumer demands. ebbits brings to SatisFactory, the expertise in the development of secure and reliable network and communication infrastructure and the control of large-scale complex systems in manufacturing lines interconnecting legacy systems with smart dependable multi-radio wireless sensor networks.

4. FUNCTIONAL VIEW

This chapter provides the overall functional architecture of the SatisFactory platform and an overview of its main components, their functionalities and interactions.

4.1 OVERALL SATISFACTORY FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE

Figure 4 shows the overall SatisFactory functional architecture that has been designed on the basis of the requirements and use cases identified within WP1 and reported in deliverables D1.1 [SatisFactory D1.1] and D1.2 [SatisFactory D1.2], respectively.

Figure 4. Component Diagram of the Overall SatisFactory Platform.

As it can be seen from Figure 4, the overall architecture is organized in five layers, namely Physical, Decision, Facility, Service and Attractive User Interface (UI) Layers. The *Physical Layer* coincides with the Smart Sensor Network component that includes all the physical components (e.g., cameras, Ultra Wide Band (UWB) wearable devices, AR devices, HMIs, Automation System – I/O Field Network and the Dependable Network Infrastructure) that interact with the shop floor and

actors. The *Decision Layer* corresponds to the Integrated Decision Support System (DSS) component, which provides decision on the basis of feedback coming from the shop floor, such as incidents, changes to manufacturing operations and processes, and also maintenance operations and schedules. Thus, this layer provides actionable knowledge and recommendations to the *Facility Layer*, which includes the Semantic Context Framework, safety related modules (i.e., Gesture&Content Recognition, Multi-Media and Localization Managers), AR-In Factory Platform and the SatisFactory Repository. In particular, the *Facility Layer* provides safety and AR related data to the upper layer, which is the *Service Layer*. It includes the Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence, Collaborative Tools, Readaptation Toolkit, and Training Education Platform components. The *Service Layer* provides services that aim to improve workers' satisfaction (through collaboration and training functionalities) as well as to provide re-adaptation features. All the three layers (i.e., *Decision*, *Facility* and *Service*) interact with and provide visualization data to the *Attractive UI Layer*, which includes UI components such as: Visual Analytics Module, AR Glasses UI, other AR UIs, and adaptable Smartphone and Tablet UI. The glue of the SatisFactory platform is represented by the Middleware, which includes two main subcomponents: Device Manager and Event Manager. In particular, the Device Manager provides the instruments to simplify the integration of heterogeneous physical devices while the Event Manager provides publisher-subscribe based notification mechanisms to the other SatisFactory components and services. However, for big amount of data, ad-hoc direct message exchanging among components is also possible.

4.2 OVERVIEW OF THE MAIN COMPONENTS

This section introduces the main components of the SatisFactory platform presenting their main functionalities, interactions and APIs.

4.2.1 Smart Sensor Network

The Smart Sensor Network (SSN) consists of heterogeneous devices that allow the interaction between the physical world and the SatisFactory framework. Some devices foreseen by the identified use cases are thermal and depth cameras as well as wearable UWB-based localization devices to be used for the workers' safety, AR-devices such as glasses, legacy/novel HMIs, and automation systems – I/O field networks that integrate legacy sensors (e.g., flow, pressure, temperature). Finally, this component includes the Dependable Network Infrastructure sub-component that is responsible for providing robust, reliable and safe communication infrastructure following the data collection and distribution tasks.

4.2.1.1 Dependable Network Infrastructure

This component guarantees communication robustness and correct data delivery in harsh radio propagation environments. This infrastructure hosts the sensing and actuation applications that integrate physical-world events from the shop floor into the cyber-world following an IoT approach. This component contributes to the supply of information to the SatisFactory knowledge-base in order to enable context-aware applications.

In order to ensure dependability, this component employs the following set of enabling features:

D2.1 - SatisFactory System Architecture

- Multi-radio connectivity: exploiting multiple network interfaces in a complementary way to guarantee communication robustness in harsh radio propagation environments.
- Intelligent functions: leveraging on cognitive techniques to enable self-configuration capabilities, such as discovery, adaptation and healing.
- Cooperative methods: exploit a number of collaborating IoT devices, in terms of sensing and computation capabilities, in order to achieve complex tasks more accurately and efficiently, as well as to improve context extraction.
- Secure data exchange: ensuring information integrity in order to reliably identify scenarios that may compromise the safety of workers.
- Power management: enabling devices to adopt different operation profiles for handling processing and communications capabilities.

The architecture of the Dependable Network Infrastructure is depicted in Figure 5. Two main components are observed: the Physical-World Gateway and the Wireless Sensor and Actuator Network.

The Physical-World Gateway is responsible for (i) collecting and processing the WSA data, (ii) administering the WSA operations at network and application levels and (iii) exposing WSA resources and capabilities to the SatisFactory framework, via the middleware. The Physical-World Gateway hosts the following functions:

- Gateway Workflow Management: coordinates the operations of the Gateway's internal functions.
- Physical-World Resource Abstraction: interacts with the raw data and protocols of the WSA and creates virtual resources corresponding to those of the real devices.
- Multi-Radio Communications: administers the utilization of the network interfaces at the WSA, based on application requirements, network performance and spectrum conditions. This function consists of a number of sub-components as shown in Figure 6.
- Security Mechanisms: hosts encryption based security method at the network or transport layers, such as IPSec or DTLS respectively, in order to ensure the integrity of the data exchanged between the WSA and the Gateway.
- Application Data Processing: provides application-related events and information, obtained from the shop floor, to consumer applications at the SatisFactory framework.
- RESTful Server: provides the SatisFactory framework an access to the WSA resources adopting a rest-based service architecture style, via the Physical-World Monitoring & Control API.

The Wireless Sensor and Actuator Network (WSA) comprises the logical and physical modules that carry out the user application at the networked embedded devices level. It consists of the following functions:

- Sensing and Actuation: enables interaction with the physical quantities of the shop floor, obtaining information and applying control/corrective actions.
- Energy Management: evaluates the operational and application status of the embedded devices and controls the power supply to the connected peripherals.
- Radio Communications: carries out the data exchange between the embedded devices and the Gateway. The function also determines the network interface and the radio parameters

to be used based on instructions from the Multi-Radio Communications function of the WSAN Gateway.

- Security Mechanisms: interacts with the Security Mechanisms function of the WSAN Gateway in order to secure the data exchange.
- Self-Configuration: implements intelligent algorithms at device level to dynamically adapt its local behaviour according to context information, such as network discovery and healing, network interface status and utilization and other application-related actions.
- Object cooperation: supports the execution of different tasks collaboratively among embedded devices, including sensing, actuation, computation and communication in order to perform complex tasks more efficiently.

Figure 5. Dependable Network Infrastructure Component Diagram.

Figure 6. Multi-Radio Communications Component Diagram.

Table 2 shows the main APIs of the Dependable Network Infrastructure component.

Table 2. Dependable Network Infrastructure main APIs.

Dependable Network Infrastructure API	Network	Description
Physical-World Monitoring & Control API		This interface exposes the resources and capabilities of the underlying system to the SatisFactory framework. It enables SatisFactory system operators to display information related to the sensing application events and parameters as well as networking status. It also provides actuation and control capabilities related to the application and the network.
Dependable Communication API		This is an internal interface that enables the exchange of raw data between the WSAN Gateway and WSAN devices. In the uplink, this interface delivers sensing and networking related data to the Gateway. While in the downlink, this API distributes application control and actuation commands to the embedded devices.

4.2.2 Integrated DSS

Integrated Decision Support System is responsible for providing feedback to the decision makers regarding immediate actions needed in response to shop floor incidents, together with changes to manufacturing operations and processes and also maintenance operations and schedules. In order for the component to be able to provide actionable knowledge and recommendations, it needs inputs from the Smart Sensor Network (through the Device Manager), the overall model of Production and Maintenance activities (through SatisFactory Repository) and context – aware knowledge stemming from the Ontology Manager. The outputs of the component are mainly events (e.g. Reaction to Incident detection, re-adaptation of the production processes, re-scheduling of maintenance activities, etc.), which through the Event Manager can trigger actions in any other component of SatisFactory (e.g. Context-aware and AR enabled HMIs) which has subscribed for notifications of these events. Based on the above, the main components that interact with Integrated DSS are Device Manager, Event Manager, SatisFactory Repository and Ontology Manager. The high level functional architecture of Integrated DSS component is depicted in the following figure:

Figure 7. Integrated DSS Component Diagram.

Table 3. Integrated DSS main APIs.

Integrated DSS API	Description
SSN Measurements	This is a required interface. Maintenance toolkit, which is a sub-component of Integrated DSS, monitors and supervises in real time the production processes in order to diagnose possible problems, flaws or malfunctions and triggers events for activating maintenance procedures or safety mechanisms. In order for the above to happen, maintenance toolkit needs a constant flow of measurements, stemming mainly from Legacy Sensors. These measurements will be provided by an interface of the Device Manager, which must expose Events that signal capturing of new measurements and also from the Satisfactory Repository which should provide Service methods using the RESTful architectural pattern, that return a collection of measurement events for a given sensor over a specific period of time.
Context-Aware Knowledge	This is a required interface. In order for the Integrated DSS to provide recommendations, the component must be able to “understand” the environment into which it operates. In other words, the decision support system must be able to get hold of implicit and explicit knowledge regarding manufacturing processes and operations, maintenance schedules and procedures, production plans and details, worker activities and availability. This knowledge must be based in well-defined vocabularies, which could provide the ability for reasoning and inference, so a SPARQL endpoint which will return RDF triples of de-referenceable URI’s will be expected.

UI and AR Events	<p>This is a supplied interface, which will be used mainly by HMIs. The shop floor feedback engine will take as an input incidents detected by the Incident Management Tools, pair them with corresponding response procedures and provide feedback to the shop floor in terms of actionable knowledge and recommendations. This feedback will have the form of events, which will be published to any subscriber interested in executing some action – based on that event. Context aware and AR enabled HMIs will mainly consume these events, in order to either inform the end users for specific incidents that have happened on the shop floor or support the decision makers for specific actions needed to be decided on production processes or maintenance procedures.</p>
Production Model	<p>This is a required interface. Production Activities tools, which is a sub-component of Integrated DSS, needs to detect the operating status of production lines in order to decide if there are flaws or malfunctions on parts of it. In such a case it must initiate an alarm, which will finally publish a number of events to all registered subscribers. These tools need an API provided by SatisFactory Repository, which will expose a number of methods returning static and dynamic data regarding products, production facilities and processes in order to build the overall production model.</p>

4.2.3 *Sematic Context Manager*

The Semantic Context Manager will be implemented using the Open Semantic Framework architecture. The Open Semantic Framework (OSF) is an integrated software stack using semantic technologies for knowledge management. It has a layered architecture that combines existing open source software with additional open source components developed specifically to provide a complete semantic technology framework. The premise of the entire stack is based on the RDF (Resource Description Framework) data model. RDF provides the ready means for integrating existing structured data assets in any format, with semi-structured data like XML and HTML, and with unstructured documents or text.

The OSF framework is made operational via ontologies that capture the domain or knowledge space, matched with internal ontologies that guide OSF operations and data display. This design approach is known as ODapps, for ontology-driven applications. Mediating the natural semantic differences that arise between people, departments and other actors in the information space is done by employing best practices for ontology and vocabulary construction. Main characteristics of this component are given below.

- Data is generally exposed (and universally available) as linked data
- SPARQL endpoints and APIs are generally RESTful in design
- The overall architecture of the SCM component is modular

The OSF Web services are generally RESTful in design and are based on HTTP and Web protocols and open standards. For the needs of SatisFactory, there is a set of web services covering

functionality in CRUD, Revision, Search, Authentication, Dataset Management, Converter and Ontology management.

The functionality of the Web services layer is based on controlling and interacting with the OSF Engines. Using the common RDF data model means that all web services and actions against the data only need to be programmed via a single, "canonical" form. Simple converters convert external, native data formats to the RDF form at time of ingest; similar converters can translate the internal RDF form back into native forms for export (or use by external applications). This use of a "canonical" form leads to a simpler design at the core of the stack and a uniform basis to which tools or other work activities can be written.

The OSF Engines governs the index and management of all OSF content. Documents are indexed by the full-text search engine, while information about their structural characteristics and metadata are stored in an RDF Database, called a "triple store". The schema aspects of the information (the ontologies) are separately managed and manipulated with their own W3C standard application, the OWL API. At ingest time, the system automatically routes and indexes the content into its appropriate stores. Another engine is available for semi-automatic assistance in tagging input information and other natural language processing (NLP) tasks.

Finally, the Semantic Context Manager (SCM) has 4 ports: 1 input and 3 outputs. The Semantic Context Manager consumes data from the SatisFactory Repository. The OSF Engines work in background, while the OSF Web Services provide an interface for interaction with other components, such as the Integrated DSS and AR IN-Factory Platform

Figure 8. Semantic Context Manager Component Diagram.

Table 4. Semantic Context Manager main APIs.

Semantic Context Manager API	Description
PHP API	<p>The SCM RESTful Web services layer may be accessed directly via API or command line, or may be controlled and interacted with using standard content management systems (CMSs).</p> <p>All web services are exposed via APIs and SPARQL endpoints. Each request to an individual web service returns an HTTP status and optionally a document of result sets. Each results document can be serialized in many ways, and may be expressed as either RDF, pure XML, JSON, or different flavours of irON to be included, such as analysis or advanced inference engines.</p>

4.2.4 AR In-Factory Platform

This component has the responsibility to provide highly specialized services, maximizing the prerogatives of Augmented Reality, in order to support workers at their workplace in a more effective and appealing way. The services offered are distinguished in two specific groups: 1) support to employees in conducting specific operating procedures; 2) support to employees by providing them advanced information and content. The AR Platform allows to provide these

services for all main types of procedures required by the project (Training, Assembly, Maintenance), and for the various situations in which these procedures and information content may be of added value (standard and/or planned activities, management of emergency situations).

The services of the first group make innovative instruments available to the end user which support the implementation of operative procedures. Following an approach both "on the job", and in "simulated environment", these tools guide users in their activity by presenting the step by step procedures interactively, by providing guidance on tools, materials, and components involved and to use. The presentation took place beneath the services offered by the Attractive Interface Layer, thus from innovative HMIs.

The services of the second group are designed instead to convey, within the visualization tools made available by the AR Platform, information and content both pre-packaged and generated at runtime by other components of the architecture (first among all those related to the Service Layer, obtained and/or constructed by services exposed from Facility Layer and from Middleware). The ecosystem of SatisFactory in fact, includes a wide variety of information and content that is important to notify the end users as a result of processes operating separately (e.g. alarm notifications, requests for collaboration, information from a supervisor, etc.). Using a specific API, based on the concept of "View Channel", the AR Platform allows to overcome this complexity and variety, ensuring not only a full compatibility with the current information, but anticipating the potential future evolution of the components.

From the point of view of its composition, the AR In-Factory Platform includes a certain number of end-use applications, that can be divided into: (a) creation tools of operative procedures for the Augmented Reality: AR Semantic Editor, AR OP Editor and AR OP "on-the-job" Editor; (b) tools for interactive visualization of procedures in the AR on several devices: AR OP GlassUP Viewer, AR OP Mobile Viewer; which moreover expose services related to the delivery of advanced information and content indicated above. Although not expressly stated in architectural layout of SatisFactory, it should be emphasized that these tools, parallel to the integration with the Middleware component, directly support different physical devices (AR Glasses, Tablet, etc.), in order to obtain a real-time visualization, normally bound to applications of AR and VR.

As is evident, this component depends on and interacts in its work with various other components of the architecture. Below is shown a high-level architectural detail of the component discussed:

Figure 9. AR In-Factory Platform Component Diagram.

The following is a high level explanation of the main interfaces, both those made available and those which request other components:

Table 5. AR In-Factory Platform main APIs.

AR In-Factory Platform	Description
Operative Procedure Management	This is a provided interface. It allows an external component to exploit the high specialization of AR Viewers relative to the management and interactive visualization of operative procedures. Among the main features of this API are: (a) activation and loading of a specific operative procedure on the AR Viewer with which the external component interacts; (b) control of the running state of such a procedure (e.g. start, stop, reset, remove, etc.); (c) control of the display modes of the procedure, in AR or in VR, in such a way as to meet both the requirements on-the-job, and in simulated environment; (d) activation and management of an integrated logging system, by which trace all the useful information accumulated during the progress of the procedure itself (e.g.: timestamps, events, interactions, etc.); by using the API you can get this log at any time.

<p>View Channel Management</p>	<p>This is a provided interface. It allows the AR Viewers to become the front-end to many specialized services supplied by higher level (Service Layer) and by lower-level (Decision Layer and Facility Layer), without knowing them. The API implements a specific paradigm for the submission of information based on the concept of "View Channel". It is a way to deliver content specific, pre-packaged and/or generated at runtime by the external components, which are displayed interactively using the HMI's made available by AR Viewers. The API decouples the contents to display by way of presenting them to the end user. Among the main features of this API we find: (a) opening, management and closure of a specific View Channel; (b) sending a data packet within the View Channel and describing the content to be displayed interactively; among the manageable content are: messages (text, audio), images, video, 3D content, etc.; (c) control of the running method linked to View Channel and synchronization with the external components.</p>
<p>AR Operating Procedures & Resources</p>	<p>This is a required interface. The SatisFactory Repository Component must provide the services through which saving and loading the data packets describing the operating procedures in the form that can be used by AR Tools and, at the same time, also provides all the resources associated with these procedures (e.g. , 3D models, images, video, etc.).</p>
<p>Physical Devices Management</p>	<p>This is a required interface. The Middleware Component must provide services to obtain data from the Smart Sensor Network component. The AR Platform expects that these data are not in "raw" form but, as required by the project, are already integrated and homogenized.</p>

4.2.5 SatisFactory Repository

SatisFactory Repository (Common Information Data Exchange Model) is responsible for storing the static and the real-time dynamic information acquired from various heterogeneous sources in the shop floor in a uniform way. All the shop floor information will be translated and presented in an understandable form, so as all SatisFactory components use them. It will contain information about the shop floor static information such as building architectural map, actors, procedures, equipment related to the project, installed sensors, Augmented Reality (AR) models that will be used, etc. Furthermore, it will include the dynamic aspects related to the shop floor, including events and context information (e.g. location, time, etc.), alerts, measurements, events related to re-adaptation and training activities, AR events, events related to gamification processes and social platform, etc. The Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM) will mainly interact with LinkSmart middleware, which will collect all the information from the shop floor, translate them to a

common vocabulary and store them to the CIDEM. So, all Satisfactory components will be able to store their output data (events, measurements, etc.) to the CIDEM through middleware. Furthermore, CIDEM will be able to provide the historical data and information related to the shop floor to all Satisfactory components. This information will also be performed through middleware. In other words, each Satisfactory component will send a data request event to the middleware, which in sequence will communicate with CIDEM, retrieve the data and send them back to the component that made the request. The high level functional architecture of Satisfactory Repository (CIDEM) is depicted in the following figure:

Figure 10. Satisfactory Repository Component Diagram.

Table 6. Satisfactory Repository main APIs.

Integrated DSS API	Description
Raw data & metadata	This is a required interface. In order for the Satisfactory Repository to store all the shop floor information, it will be provide to middleware services so as to store raw data, measurements, events and metadata to the repository. This information will be based in well-defined vocabularies.
Historical data & models	This is a required interface. In order for the Satisfactory Repository to send historical information to the Satisfactory components (after having request them from the middleware), it will provide services to the middleware to retrieve these data. This information will be based on well-defined vocabularies.

4.2.6 Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence

Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence is responsible for providing real-time diagnostics and control actions to the operators at nominal conditions of shop floor operation. The platform communicates directly with the middleware component and the Decision Support System (through middleware) in order to derive the optimum actions based on the current state of the machines and

the worker’s behaviour. It is responsible for providing an overview of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), personalized notes and tasks that are adjusted per worker. Additionally, AR platform will integrate and present the Semantic Context and the Collaborative tools through an easy to use and intuitive interface. The high level functional architecture of Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence is depicted in the following figure:

Figure 11. Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence Component Diagram.

Table 7. Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence main APIs.

Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence API	Description
Raw data, metadata, historical data & models	This is a required interface. The Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence will request and retrieve all the needed historical and real-time data from the CIDEM through middleware. All this information will be useful for the analysis of the shop floor operation.
Metadata	This is a required interface. All the information extracted from the platform (e.g. real-time diagnostics, control actions to the operators, etc.) will be sent for storage and further use by other components to the CIDEM through the middleware.
KPIs, Personalized notes & tasks adjusted per worker	This is a required interface. All the KPIs, personalized notes and tasks adjusted per worker, as estimated and extracted by the platform, will be sent to the SatisFactory components and to the CIDEM for storage through the middleware.

4.2.7 Collaborative Tools

The Collaborative Tools incorporate the Social Interaction and Cooperation component. This provides a platform that workers can use to interact with their (remote) colleagues. It can be used to cooperate on work related issues, e.g., requesting for help for a particular problem or for sharing off-topic interests. It is designed for usage inside the shop floor, i.e. users will use the system when not

sitting on their computers in the office environment. This requires the equipment of mobile or ubiquitous user interfaces which are elaborated within the adaptable user interfaces task. The final choice of the particular user interface will be made based on the specific requirement of the social interaction and cooperation use case.

Figure 12. Collaborative Tools Component Diagram.

Table 8. Collaborative Tools main APIs.

Collaborative Tools API	Description
Connect to other SatisFactory Components	This is a required interface. The social collaboration platform needs to communicate with other components. These components are used to capture input for the social interaction and collaboration platform or to provide output, usually to the user interface that is viewed by the end user. The input can also come from that interface or it can be data that is imported or captured from external systems such as sensors or intra-factory systems. The middleware provides the necessary functionality for network connection and interoperability. Furthermore, the Event Manager of the Middleware is used for event-based data transmission.
Get Location	This is a required interface. When the social interaction and collaboration platform processes data that is based on the location of workers or when the input or output interface is dependent on the location of the workers, this location data is requested from the Localization Manager.
Input/Output	This is a required interface. It incorporates the interfaces between the social interaction and collaboration platform and the user interfaces. The adaptable user interfaces provide functionalities to present the output from the collaborative tools to the end user or to gather input from them.

4.2.8 Re-adaptation Toolkit

The toolkit for the re-adaptation of existing facilities and human resource balancing will be developed within task 2.4, which started at M8 and concludes at M30. At the moment, only a preliminary scouting has been performed, in order to reach a common understanding in terms of a list of functionalities belonging to this component. Furthermore, some of the expected outputs have also been identified.

The re-adaptation toolkit will have the scope of carefully evaluating factory parameters, elaborating them, and performing complex data analysis in order to visually provide suggestion lists to:

- increase efficiency of existing facilities
- quickly react to predefined events
- balance the workload of human resources according to specific requirements

It is also in scope of this toolkit to describe the flow of process concerning involved workplaces through the analysis of statistic data coming from the production environment.

In details data from the Smart Sensor network and other events coming from the Event Manager will be analysed and, if needed, compared with data stored in the repositories. Consequently the action of elaborating data flows with Markov chains based algorithms and models of the existing facilities will take place, with the aim to define and model occupancy levels.

The re-adaptation toolkit will work under the assumption that the shop floor will be conveniently abstracted in order to guarantee a certain level of interoperability of modules and sub-components across different facilities.

Further details about this component will be added in the next iteration of this deliverable when activities related to its design and development will start.

4.2.9 Training and Educational Platform

This component has the responsibility to provide dedicated services to support the activities of training and education not only to workers and machinery operators but also to manufacturing process supervisor. The main feature of this platform is the ability to manage, in an innovative way, the creation of content for training and, especially, its use. The Training Platform in fact, optimizes its effectiveness by focusing on the technologies of Augmented Reality, on the exploitation of a new generation of HMIs and on the adoption of an approach to training "on the job".

This component is developed on top of AR In-Factory Platform, but is able to take advantage of the specialized services offered by several other members of the Facility Layer and of the Middleware. Thanks to the integration with the platform of AR, the Training component inherits all of its major powers such as: a) support to the description and presentation of procedures related to all areas required (Training, Manufacturing, Maintenance); b) support to the creation and use of standard procedures related both to common or planned activities, and to emergency situations; c) support to the creation of condition-based procedures; d) support to the services offered both on-the-job and in a simulated environment; e) use of specific content perfectly integrated into HMIs inherited by AR Tools.

Beyond the functionality inherited from the platform of AR, this component can provide several highly specialized services, deemed necessary in order to increase the level of involvement of the trainees; they are: a) support to a bidirectional communication between the trainees and their supervisor (or, in any case, between the novice and the expert), in order to increase the passage of knowledge; b) support to a transfer of information and data between the tools made available to the trainees and their supervisor; c) implementation of features specifically related to the management of a training session: performance measurement, comparison with previous sessions, analysis of results and provision of indices and specific information, etc.

From the point of view of its composition, the Training Platform includes a highly specialized tool for training, diversified into four variants to cover both physical configurations to support (GlassUp AR

Devices, Mobile Devices) and the different roles of the user (trainee, supervisor). Different instances of the tool of training have the opportunity to communicate with each other, allowing it to provide the services described above. Also for the Training Platform, the description of training operating procedures is done through the tools developed for the platform of AR, namely: the AR Semantic Editor, AR OP Editor and AR OP "on the job" Editor. Finally, in this case as well it is useful to emphasize that the applications of training, as well as being able to interact via the Middleware with the Physical Layer, directly support physical devices, in order to maintain their maximum performance always.

Figure 13 shows the high level architectural detail of the component discussed, in which the connections with the other components are highlighted:

Figure 13. Training and Educational Platform Component Diagram.

The Training Platform does not expose specific interfaces to other components of the architecture. Instead it depends necessarily on interfaces requests to several other system components. The following is a brief breakdown of these interfaces:

Table 9. Training and Educational Platform main APIs.

Training and Educational Platform API	Description
Operative Procedure Management	This is an interface requested to the AR In-Factory Platform. This API must allow access and exploit the highly specialized services related to the management and visualization of operative procedures, included in the

	platform of AR. Moreover, the same API should provide good support to the logging of procedures performed, containing all of the essential information on which the Training Platform builds its specialized services (e.g. benchmarking of achieved performance).
View Channel Management	This is an interface requested to the AR In-Factory Platform. This API must allow all content specifically designed for training to vehicular at runtime, towards the visualization tools made available by the AR platform.
AR Operating Procedures & Resources	This is an interface requested to SatisFactory Repository. The latter must provide services through which you can save and load the data packets describing the training operating procedures and simultaneously all the resources associated with these procedures (e.g. 3D models, images, video).
Physical Devices Management	This interface is required to the Middleware. The latter must provide services through which you can get data from the component Smart Sensor Network. The Training Platform is expects that this information is not provided in the "raw" form but, as per the requirements of the project, is already integrated and homogenized.

4.2.10 Multi Modal and Augmented HMIs

This component has the responsibility to provide the best user experience for all specialized applications developed within SatisFactory. The scope of this module is not only to provide as much as possible a uniform look-and-feel and optimized for different typology of considered devices, which takes into account the ergonomic issues (e.g. minimizing the cognitive effort for users), but also to reduce the need for the developers of the applications to re-invent user interaction solutions for similar situations. Thus resulting in a cost reduction and shorten delivery time. Even more, it tries to follow the most innovative approaches currently applied in the best known experiences, documented in literature, in this area.

Each software deliverable of the project, which has to do with a user, needs a proper and specific HMI. Nevertheless, in order to maximize the innovative approaches and technologies of SatisFactory, it is very important to uniform the HMIs to be developed by fitting them with the adopted physical device, the specific use cases and the chosen "attractive and gamification" approaches. The key approach in this case is to provide a comprehensive specification for the requested HMIs, that each software applications and systems have to realize considering their specific implementation environment. Anyway, high specialized architectural components (e.g. AR In-Factory Platform) can share software modules and/or services to simplify the implementation of concrete HMIs for the demanding external components.

For all practical purposes, it is useful to consider this component as a specialized module, strongly reusable and integrable into all specific applications and systems provided with SatisFactory. By doing this, it is possible here to describe it as a set of specific sub-components and APIs.

Hardware UI Component

It is the sub component directly related to the capabilities of the physical devices used to implement the HMIs for SatisFactory applications and systems. It is built in features provided by:

- AR Glasses (by GlassUP)
- Wearable Devices (by GlassUP and 3th parts)
- Mobile Devices (for instance Tablet, Smartphones etc.)
- Desktop PCs

It also includes management of the following aspects:

- Worker's Input:
 - Touch [Type and Press] (e.g. Touch Screen of a Table, keyboard)
 - Speech (e.g. Microphone)
 - Body [body movement, gesture] (e.g. Camera, Motion Tracking System)
- Output to Worker:
 - Display (e.g. AR Glasses, Tablet display)
 - Text to speech (e.g. Speakers, Headphones)
 - Audio (e.g. Speakers, Headphones)

Multi Modal UI Component

It's the sub component, implemented as a set of highly specialized software modules, which can support most of the common multimodal interfaces, by combining different hardware-provided input modes such as touch, speech, touch (tactile), gestures, head and body movements. The advantage of using these multi modal inputs is that the multiple modalities increase usability and provide the users with more possibilities to switch from one input mode to another that may be better suited to a particular task or setting. Complementarily the same component manages all output devices, by guaranteeing a specific content to be provided to the worker, fits the best channel possible (audio, visual, etc.).

GUI Component

This sub component implements specific graphical user interfaces, useful to support the designed HMIs, allowing to apply all innovative approaches of VR, AR and gamification requested by the project. It's based on a Model-View pattern for a flexible structure in which the interface is independent from and indirectly linked to application functionality, so the GUI can be easily customized.

Figure 14. High level Multi Modal & Augmented HMIs Component Diagram.

Specialized UI Components

They represent modules, designed and implemented as specialization of above shown UI components. Their presence is caused from the several innovative approaches and functionalities requested by the project. These components are directly built on top of other architectural ones (e.g. AR In-Factory Platform, Collaborative Tools, etc.). The most important Specialized UI components are:

- AR UI
- Collaboration/Communication UI
- Visual Analytics Module UI

Figure 15. Specialized UI Component Diagram.

The following is a high level explanation of the main interfaces provided by Multi Modal & Augmented HMIs component.

Table 10. Multi Modal and Augmented HMI main APIs.

Multi Modal and Augmented HMI API	Description
Input Channel Management	This is a provided interface. It allows to obtain data acquired by physical devices and managed by Multi Modal UI, in order to handle them. From an application point of view, this API uncouples physical HMIs and specialized multi modal services from the application layer. The handling of GUI can directly call this API as well.
Output Channel Management	This is a provided interface. It allows to send data, generated by specialized architectural modules, to physical devices, passing through the management of Multi Modal UI. From an application point of view, this API uncouples physical HMIs and specialized multi modal services from the application layer. The handling of GUI can directly call this API as well.

5. MIDDLEWARE AS A SUPPORTING INFRASTRUCTURE

In SatisFactory, the LinkSmart Middleware will be used to integrate existing automation systems, sensor networks, and augmented reality devices with their solutions to be developed within the scope of the project. Below we present an introduction and architecture of the LinkSmart middleware.

5.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE LINKSMART MIDDLEWARE

The LinkSmart middleware has its origins in the FP6 IP Hydra [Hydra]. It was developed under the lead of Fraunhofer FIT. After the project ended, the resulting Hydra middleware was renamed to LinkSmart and it was released open source. From that time on, the middleware is continuously matured by different international partners, among them FIT and ISMB.

The main purpose of LinkSmart is to give application developers a tool which handles the heterogeneity of physical devices for them. As a result, developers can easily use web service interfaces for controlling any kind of network technology, such as Bluetooth, RF, ZigBee, RFID, Wi-Fi, etc. Further features of LinkSmart are secure peer-to-peer (P2P) communication, device and service discovery, and respective developer tools.

LinkSmart uses a service-oriented architecture (SOA) approach in order to offer support across platforms and network boundaries. This higher level generalizes core features, such as security, trust and reflective properties. LinkSmart has been evaluated in several applications in ubiquitous computing domains including eHealth and (Energy-aware) Smart Homes [Al-Akkad et al., 2009], [Eikerling et.al, 2009], [Jahn et al., 2010], [Reiners et al., 2009].

5.2 LINKSMART ARCHITECTURE

LinkSmart divides between devices, which can directly run the middleware, and those devices, which are too resource-constrained to run it. The latter ones are connected via a dedicated gateway device to the LinkSmart network. These gateways have a wired or wireless connection to the resource-constrained device. The gateways run Device Proxies, which handle the communication to the resource-constrained device and translate it to LinkSmart. From the service point of view, the communication with a proxy is identical to a communication with a native LS device. Devices which are not able to directly run LinkSmart can be further classified into D1, D2 and D3 devices.

Main components in LinkSmart are managers. A LinkSmart manager encapsulates a set of operations and data that realize a specific functionality.

Figure 16 shows a typical LinkSmart deployment including components and interactions. It includes six LinkSmart connected devices: Three of them can directly run LinkSmart. The other three are connected to the same LinkSmart gateway.

Each connected device runs a Network Manager (NM), which registers all services belonging to the device. All communication between devices runs through the Network Managers. So, network services are accessed through the own Network Manager. The Network Managers are connected to

Security Managers (SM) and Crypto Managers (CM), which secure, encrypt and decrypt the communication.

Figure 16. LinkSmart Example Device Network.

5.3 EVENT MANAGER

The Event Manager provides a means of communicating events between components. For this, it implements a publish/subscribe mechanism. In this approach, the Event Manager plays the role of the event broker. That is the central component which manages subscriptions, provides a method for publishing events and finally, it distributes events to subscriber components. This way, the Event Manager achieves a decoupling in space, time and synchronization. The high level interaction of LinkSmart Event Manager with various other components of the SatisFactory architecture is depicted in Figure 17.

Figure 17. LinkSmart Component Diagram.

Figure 18 shows the typical interaction with the Event Manager on a theoretical, realistic example from the SatisFactory domain. In this example, two components, namely the Localization Manager and the Glasses UI, need to react on location sensor data events. So, both subscribe at the Event Manager under the topics "localizationSensorData". Every time the location sensor raises a new sensor data event, it publishes this event to the Event Manager. The Event Manager then takes care to notify all subscribers of this event type, in this case, the Localization Manager and the Glasses UI. These two components can then further process the data; for instance, they can display the data.

Figure 18. Event Manager Sequence Diagram.

5.4 DEVICE MANAGER

The Device Manager (hereafter DM) will provide the instruments to simplify heterogeneous physical devices virtualization through a common interface and technology-agnostic access to the lower layer. These devices have different capabilities, communication technologies and features. A device virtualization is so needed to help the seamlessly integration of these devices with other SatisFactory components and features. More specifically, the need is to overcome the fragmentation of vertically-oriented closed systems, architectures and application areas and move towards open systems and platforms that support multiple applications. The DM will take care of the compliance with current and upcoming standards/reference architectures and semantics-enriched representations, like: OSGi Device Abstraction Layer (OSGi DA), ETSI M2M (ETSI M2M), OneM2M (OneM2M), HGI Device (HGID), VORTO (VORTO), SAREF ontology (SAREF) and DogOnt ontology.

Figure 19. Device Manager Functional View.

The Device Manager will be able to expose devices accordingly through the combination of 3 main possible, ontology based, representations of any device, which can be summarized as: services provided by a device, events generated by a device or variables which can be configured or can be accessed by the device user. The device representation will also describe the nature of the devices itself and the characteristics of the shared information (e.g.: type and unit of measured data).

At the current stage of the Satisfactory project, the device manager is not yet architecturally defined in detail. Full specifications will be available within Task 4.5 "Integration of social collaboration and sensing environments for enhancing collective awareness", which starts at M13. At that stage, the devices requiring inclusion through the DM will be identified: this is relevant because the approach described before is not always applicable, due to some technological/physical limitation of devices or due to specific software devices' interface/protocol/API constraints.

5.5 LINKSMART MINIATURIZATION

One goal, which we aim at in Satisfactory, is the LinkSmart miniaturization. This has two purposes. Firstly, we want to make LinkSmart more lightweight so that it can better run on low resource platforms and so that it can run on more of those platforms than now. Secondly, we want to facilitate the usage of LinkSmart for application developers and improve their user experience.

For this purpose, LinkSmart will replace various old, cumbersome and proprietary protocols by up-to-date, lightweight and cumbersome ones. Firstly, LinkSmart is originally using SOAP web services. We will exchange this by the far more easy to handle REST paradigm. Coming along with this, the XML-based WSDL as description language will be replaced by the lightweight JSON format. Finally, the Event Manager so far uses a proprietary event format. It will be replaced by the standard protocol MQTT. Since MQTT brokers exist, this can lead to a complete replacement of the

current Event Manager so that an existing MQTT broker is integrated and wrapped for LinkSmart developers.

Next, a device and service catalogue will be developed, which will be used to register all devices and their corresponding services in a network. This will better allow other components to find services. In addition, the architecture and definition of devices and resources in the LinkSmart world will be checked and probably revised.

Finally, the different aspects of LinkSmart will be better separated into different sub components. One sub component will mainly deal with the integration of heterogeneous devices and communication to these devices in a local network. The other sub component will focus on the communication between different networks or over the internet. This separation allows for focusing on problems at different levels and scenarios.

5.6 LINKSMART MAIN APIS

The following table contains the list of APIs which are exposed by the LinkSmart middleware. For each API, a brief description has been provided and major characteristics have been highlighted.

Middleware API	Description	Required Interface	Provided Interface
Device-Specific Sensor Access	Each individual sensor type requires either a LinkSmart proxy or must run the Network Manager component to be accessible from the LinkSmart network. In both cases, the device specific input and output interfaces are made available as virtualized devices in the Device Manager.	x	
Get Domain Model	The Device Manager needs information about the available resources that need to be incorporated, such as communication technology and access methods, as well as their interconnection to one another.	x	
Abstracted Device Access	It represents the abstracted access to individual devices on a standardized virtualization layer. This incorporates services access and addressability. Furthermore, the interface consists of functionalities for the whole group of devices. Other SatisFactory components can list the available resources and search within the list.		x
Publish	When SatisFactory components raise an event, they publish it at the Event Manager using this method. The Event Manager publishes the event to all the components which subscribed to the topic of the event. An event consists of a topic, the message payload and QoS parameters.		x

Subscribe	Satisfactory components can subscribe to a topic for which they want to receive events. The Event Manager publishes an event to the subscribed components every time an event with the particular topic is raised.		x
Notify	Every component which has subscribed to an event topic must implement this interface. It is called by the Event Manager every time an event with the subscribed topic is raised.	x	
Get Semantic Device Data	The device information that the Device Manager gets from the Domain Models is augmented by semantic information about the resources provided by the Semantic Context Manager.	x	
Store	Every event, which is running through the Event Manager is stored at the Repository for later processing and logging. Event data is transferred from Event Manager to Repository through this interface.	x	

6. DEPLOYMENT VIEW

The deployment view focuses on aspects of the system that are important after the system has been tested and is ready to go live. This view defines the physical environment in which the system is intended to run, including:

- Required hardware environment (e.g. processing nodes, network interconnections, etc.)
- Technical environment requirements for each node
- Mapping of software elements to the runtime environment
- Third-party software requirements
- Network requirements

The deployment view needs to document the required deployment environment of the SatisFactory platform, which depends on the pilot areas and their topology. This chapter provides a first overview, covering the known hardware requirements of the software modules and used tools.

A first component diagram indicating the deployment view of the SatisFactory components is depicted in Figure 20. The smart sensor network is comprised by a variety of heterogeneous sensors (bottom of the figure) including the preinstalled factory's automation system which provides information about the production activities and the status of the factory's infrastructure. Furthermore, it is comprised by the UWB wearable and UWB anchor, as well as other sensors (such as gyrometers, accelerometers etc.) which will be used within the SatisFactory project. All these sensors/devices will be connected to the Middleware Device Manager through corresponding gateways, which will forward the information from the shop floor to the Middleware. The Device Manager, running in a dedicated PC named *IoT Gateway*, is equipped with all the necessary drivers, so as to understand and interpret the multi-sensorial information. The Device Manager is interconnected with the Middleware Event Manager, which could be located to the same PC (i.e., *IoT Gateway*) or even to another workstation as it is depicted in Figure 20. The integrated DSS is interconnected with the Middleware Device Manager in order to acquire data stemming from the smart sensor network. This information is subsequently processed, generating recommendations which are then provided to users or other subsystems in the form of Events through the Event Manager.

The Augmented Reality (AR) glasses could be though in this stage as another sensor, which will be connected to the Device Manager with a dedicated Radio Module GW and exchange messages/events with the rest of the SatisFactory components through it. At the time of writing, the type of AR glasses radio technology has not been selected yet. This activity will be done within Task 4.1.

Figure 20. SatisFactory Deployment View Architecture.

All SatisFactory components, which will be connected among each other with the Middleware Event Manager, could be installed either to the same PC workstation or distributed to a number of PCs. Figure 20 illustrates the case where the SatisFactory components are distributed to various PC workstations, e.g. one for the integrated DSS, one for the Semantic Context Manager, Collaborative tools, Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence, Repository, Localization manager, Multi-media manager, Gesture content recognition manager, AR In-Factory platform and the Training and Educational platform. All these SatisFactory components composes the cloud based SatisFactory infrastructure and will be interconnected among each other with a dedicated or not intranet, which could be either wired or wireless or even a combination of both.

It is worth mentioning that HMIs are directly connected to the Device Manager and exchange messages to the SatisFactory components through it. Finally, cameras, which will be used within SatisFactory, will be handled as special devices. Since the data produced by cameras is huge, Middleware and Repository are not able to handle them. So, they will be connected directly with the components that will need their information, and only the metadata (e.g. incidents, locations, etc.) will be forward to the middleware and to the repository.

6.1 SATISFACTORY COMPONENTS HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

Table 11 lists the preliminary HW requirements concerning the main SatisFactory components.

Table 11. SatisFactory Components HW Requirements.

Name	Support	Hardware Requirements
Middleware	FIT	A PC workstation will be needed with the following minimum requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • i5 CPU is preferable; • at least 4GB RAM; • 500GB hard disk; • Wi-Fi connection; • Ethernet connection; • Windows 7 operating system.
Semantic Context Manager	EPFL	See Middleware requirements.
Collaborative Tools	FIT	See Middleware requirements.
Integrated DSS	ABE	A PC workstation will be needed with the following minimum requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • i5 CPU is preferable; • at least 4GB RAM; • 500 GB hard disk; • Wi-Fi connection; • Ethernet connection; • USB connection;

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows 7 operating system.
AR In-Factory Platform (Creation Tools)	REGOLA	<p>A PC Workstation will be needed with the following minimum requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • i5 CPU (last Generation); • 4GB RAM; • 500GB hard disk; • NVidia GPU GTX 650 2GB • Wi-Fi connection; • Ethernet connection; • Windows 7 operating system.
AR In-Factory Platform (Visualization Tools – Mobile version)	REGOLA	<p>Tablet with the following minimum requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QUAD-CORE arm Cortex-A9 (set ARMv7) • 3GB RAM • 16GB ROM • Camera Front 8MP • Wi-Fi connection; • Bluetooth connection • USB connection • Display 10" • Android 4.4 (KitKat) operating system
AR In-Factory Platform (Visualization Tools – GlassUP version)	REGOLA	Definition of GlassUP hardware requirements is still in progress.
CIDEM/ Repository	CERTH	See Middleware requirements.
Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence	CERTH	See Integrated DSS requirements.
Training Educational Platform (Creation Tools)	REGOLA	See AR In-Factory Platform – (Creation Tools) requirements.
Training Educational Platform (Visualization Tools)	REGOLA	See AR In-Factory Platform – (Visualization Tools – Mobile Version) requirements.

– Mobile Version)		
Training Educational Platform (Visualization Tools – GlassUP version)	REGOLA	See AR In-Factory Platform – (Visualization Tools – GlassUP Version) requirements.
Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices	GlassUp (AR glasses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wi-Fi connection; • Wired Box connected to the glasses for batteries and UI with commands (provided by GlassUp) • USB connection for direct connections to third devices (PCs, tablets, smartphones, other)
Localization Manager, Multi-Media Manager, Gesture & Content Recognition Manager	ISMB	<p>A PC workstation will be needed with the following minimum requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • i7 CPU is preferable; • at least 8GB RAM; • 500 GB hard disk; • Wi-Fi connection; • Ethernet connection; • USB connection;

6.2 EXISTING SOFTWARE AND HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

6.2.1 Middleware

LinkSmart middleware does not have any specific hardware requirements. A basic infrastructure of the core managers (Network Manager, Event Manager, and Device Proxies) can be set up on one or more state-of-the-art workstations. Recommended requirements for such workstations are: i5 CPU, at least 4 GB RAM and 500GB hard disk.

6.2.2 Human Tracking Component

Human tracking components comprised by a depth cameras network interconnected with an aggregated system, which is able to acquire all the detected information from the cameras. Each camera should be plugged on a computer with hardware characteristics similar to the integrated DSS characteristics presented above (i5 CPU is preferable, at least 4GB RAM, 500 GB hard disk, Wi-Fi connection, Ethernet connection, USB connection, Windows 7 operating system). Furthermore, all these computers should be connected to a server with similar characteristics either wired or wireless (depending on the pilot area). Of course, all PCs should support this connection protocol.

This connection could be dedicated or not, but the server should be also connected with the rest of the SatisFactory components, in order to exchange messages and events with the middleware.

6.2.3 AR In-Factory Platform Component

In order to accomplish all advanced services that it has in charge, the AR In-Factory Platform needs to have all the necessary data by directly asking them from the Middleware. Thus it is strongly uncoupled from specific hardware requirements. The real dependencies on physical devices are instead associated to the specialized components that are in charge of the implementation of specific services. Only a few of these are directly connected to AR In-Factory Platform, while a lot of them are global services provided to all SatisFactory main components.

The software and hardware requirements for the services strictly dependent from the AR In-Factory Platform are:

- FID system (to track physical object, tools, etc.). At minimum this system will include: a RFID reader, two antennas, cables, etc. In order to not have a dedicated PC for this system, it could be plugged on an already present pc in the workplace area. A configuration like the one requested for the Middleware is more than enough.
- Set of cameras. At minimum this system will include: two high quality industrial cameras, hub, support structures, cables, etc. In order to not have a dedicated PC for this system, it could be plugged on an already present pc in the workplace area. A configuration like the one requested for the Middleware is enough.

To know the software and hardware requirements for the services provided by the other specialized components, see the paragraph related to them. Here a list of all main services from which AR In-Factory Platform needs data:

- Gesture Recognition
- Object Recognition
- Frame Acquisition
- Video Acquisition
- Smart Sensor Value Evaluation

6.2.4 Training & Education Environment Component

See information and requirements provided in previous paragraph "AR In-Factory Platform Component".

7. INFORMATION VIEW

7.1 APPLICATION DOMAIN MODEL

The information view is based on the abstraction of the shop floor in terms of semantic IoT resources corresponding to “*virtual entities*” in the IoT Architecture Reference Model (ARM) [IoT-A D1.2]. On top of that, we added the required classes and interconnections supporting the SatisFactory applications.

Due to the user-centric concept of the project, in this first iteration of the architecture we have provided an initial overview of the SatisFactory domain model focused on the training feature of the platform, see Figure 21. However, it can be extended to support other features such as collaboration, safety and re-adaptation, but it has been left for the other two subsequent iterations.

As it can be observed from Figure 21, each physical entity, which is represented by the IoT device, is extended by sensors and devices that will be deployed in the shop floor. Each sensor and device hosts some resources that can be accessed through IoT services. The resources are software components that provide information about physical entities or enable the controlling of devices. Physical entities (i.e. the IoT devices) are represented in the digital world via a virtual entity.

Note that virtual entities are associated to a single IoT device that they represent. While ideally there is only one IoT device for each virtual entity, it is possible that the same IoT device can be associated to several virtual entities. Each virtual entity must have one and only one identifier (ID) that identifies the represented object.

Focusing on the upper part of the domain model, each user (e.g. actor, machine, and tool) can interact with IoT devices and invoke the associated services.

Figure 21. Example of Satisfactory Application Domain Model.

7.2 OVERVIEW OF INFORMATION FLOW

Figure 22. SatisFactory Information Flow.

Figure 22 depicts the information flow representing the data exchanged among the main components of the SatisFactory platform. Note that sequence diagrams, which have been drawn on the basis of the use cases [SatisFactory D1.2] identified within WP1, are presented in section 9 of this document.

A brief explanation of each data is reported as follows.

- **VisualizationData:** Data to be presented to the end user.
- **HMI-InputData:** GUI Collected Data, such as Touch Data (Type & Press) or Body Data (Movement & Gesture) or Speech Data (Microphone).
- **HMI-OutputData:** Text or Image or Sounds Data.
- **RawData:** Raw data coming from sensors, cameras, etc. deployed in the shop floor
- **GamifiedData:** Contains the necessary data needed for visualizing results and info to the user in a pleasant and comfortable way.
- **ARData:** Data containing AR info.
- **DSSEvent:** Contains data extracted by the integrated DSS component.
- **TrainingEvent:** Contains data about a training event. It is raised either by the integratedDSS or by the Foreman (when the need of a new training is identified).
- **TrainingNotification:** A notification about the need of a new training. Can refer either to a Foreman (to confirm the training) or to a trainee (to start the training).
- **TrainingData:** Data from the repository related to training (also the workplace practice), such as texts, images, videos. Also contains Training Analytics Data, Collaborative Data and Channeled Information (by AR-Platform).
- **TrainEvaluationResults:** Results related to the training evaluation procedure, such as whether the trainee succeeded or not, indicating what are the failures.
- **AR-TrainingProceduresData:** Training Procedure Description and Training Procedures Resources (e.g. 3D Models, Images, Videos, Motion Data, etc.).
- **TrainingSessionsData:** Sessions Data, Analytics Data, Results Data (retrieve or store).
- **CamerasData & LegacySensorsData:** Data from cameras and legacy sensors.
- **AR-OperatingProcedures:** Operating Procedures Description and Operating Procedures Resources (e.g. 3D Models, Images, Videos, Motion Data, etc.)
- **OperatingProceduresNotification:** A notification about operating procedures.
- **OperatingProceduresData:** Data from the repository related to operating procedures, such as texts, images, videos. Also contains Operating Procedures Analytics Data, Collaborative Data and Channeled Information (by AR-Platform)
- **DepthImages:** Contains the depth images acquired by the depth sensor network.
- **OccupantFlows:** Contains data about the flows/ trajectories of the occupants in the monitored area.
- **ThermalImages:** Contains the thermal images acquired by the thermal sensor network.
- **ThermalEvent:** Contains data about events related to areas and equipment whose temperature has been suddenly and abnormally increased.
- **IncidentEvent:** Contains data about the incident events that have already happened or potentially will happen in the area covered by the depth and thermal sensor network.
- **ShopFloorInfo:** Contains the data about the shop-floor, such as building geometry, procedures, actors, sensors, etc.
- **ProductionInfo:** Contains data about the production operations in the shop-floor.

- **ShopFloorData:** Contains data about the shop-floor.
- **ShopFloorEvent:** Contains data about the events that are recorded from the multi-sensorial network installed in the shop-floor.
- **ShopFloorEvaluation:** Evaluation related to the overall shop-floor operation, combining, correlating and analyzing the heterogeneous shop-floor information from the sensor network and the metadata extracted by SatisFactory tools, such as production activity tool, incident detection, etc.
- **ProductionResults:** Results related to the production operations.
- **ShopFloorOverview:** Overview of KPIs related to the shop-floor operation.
- **PersonalizationResults:** Personalized notes and tasks that are adjusted per worker, based on the evaluation of the current status of the shop-floor operation.
- **ActionData / RecommendationData:** Data concerning actions or recommendations on actions.
- **StreamingPointInfo:** The request to acquire streams from a specific areaID or cameraID. The device manager is the component that maps the cameraID (or the areaID) with the end point for streaming (generally a URI).
- **SegmentedBlobsData:** Binary masks and vectors (segments) describing the content of the video (blobs).
- **ContextData:** Data coming from Semantic Context Manager.
- **UWBLocationData:** Data coming from UWB devices.
- **geoFencingEvent:** Virtual geofencing (e.g. for avoiding human presence on unauthorized paths and areas).
- **SafetyEvent:** e.g. automatic detection of personnel not wearing required safety equipment.
- **SafetyData:** Safety-related data (e.g. data related to an incident or to a human presence in not authorized area).

8. PERSPECTIVES

8.1 *SATISFACTION PERSPECTIVE*

The SatisFactory project approach, to perform operator satisfaction, is based on the design of user centred and value-added application which increases the attractiveness of the working environment as well as the quality of the working conditions.

In order to properly involve both end-users and stakeholders in the evaluation process, SatisFactory solutions will be simultaneously evaluated by all involved actors. This will be possible through the social interaction platform, which will support multimedia enhanced interactions among employees and will encapsulate the context-aware knowledge schemas (section 4.2.3) available through the middleware. A set of collaborative tools (section 4.2.7) that will leverage on gamification techniques to enable deployment of serious gaming oriented applications. This will, for example, enable employees to earn rewards and compete as groups, enhancing the overall user experience and driving greater participation and engagement through a friendly game competition. In the same scenario, a digital add-on system will be integrated with both panels and mobile devices (section 4.2.10), providing to operators, information on the basis of back-end elaborated task scheduling and productivity benchmarking. The SatisFactory platform will also leverage prompt abnormal events management (section 5.3), as well as robust and reliable wireless connectivity (section 4.2.1) for real-time services in hostile environment, for the benefit of the users' efficiency and feeling of satisfaction towards the production environment. Finally, the usage of innovative interactive platform (section 4.2.4), in combination with all the previously mentioned actions, shall positively stimulate user gratification and collaboration between employees, further improving the effectiveness and the acceptability of the platform.

Satisfactory will introduce the use of the Augmented Reality in a structured way, focusing primarily on the creation of a "Development Framework" through which applications will be developed to support the production environment and training activities that are in scope of the project. This framework will introduce the adoption of a development approach, oriented to increase the attractiveness of work environments and employees' satisfaction. The AR framework will be based on the development of a set of specialized tools, divided in two categories: the Creation Tool, specifically designed to describe optimized contents for AR (3D models, animations, texts, images, etc.), and Visualization Tool that will act as an enabler to visualize the created contents on a wide range of devices (i.e. mobile and wearable devices). Besides being used as standalone applications, designed to directly support assembly and maintenance activities (AR In-Factory Platform), the tool will also act as a framework to develop more specialized applications on the top of it. These applications will be mainly related to the Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence, Training & Educational Environment and Collaborative Tools.

The real challenge taken up by SatisFactory will be to take into account difficulties emerged in recent years correlated to the application of AR technologies to the industrial environment. In fact, if the number of AR applications for marketing and entertainment is now so high that it is impossible to be counted them, in the industrial field the adoption of AR has quickly proved its limits, mainly

due to the difficulty of designing effective HMIs. In fact, only in a real working environment, especially by analysing the physical and behavioural constraints of the workplace, it is possible to exploit the most out of these innovative technologies. From this point of view, the project will aim in particular to obtain the greatest possible benefits from the use of AR glasses (GlassUP) and wearable devices associated with them, through the design and implementation of advanced multi-modal HMIs (touch, speech, display, gesture recognition). Finally, the presentation of the information in the most attractive and effective way will be a challenge for the AR applications, alongside the minimization of physical interactions required by the user. Therefore, the satisfaction of final operators will not only be achieved with the use of cutting-edge technological settings, but also maximizing synergies between them.

8.2 SAFETY PERSPECTIVE

The SatisFactory project takes care of innovative instruments supporting safety and ergonomics of the working areas and of the single worker. One of these instruments is the context recognition module based on localization. The location information can be obtained by the data fusion of information coming from heterogeneous sensors (e.g., UWB and inertial sensors) as well as privacy preserving cameras. For this purpose, the context manager interacts with enabling modules such as the Localization Manager, the Multiple-Media Manager and the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager. These modules will act as enablers in order to deploy safety enhanced procedures at the shop floor level.

The Localization Manager will provide workers' position leveraging Ultra Wide Band (UWB) wearable devices and related indoor localization algorithms for real time indoor localization. Other localization schemes are based also on the processing of video streams coming from privacy preserving cameras. The workers' localization will be used to enhance safety at the shop floor level, providing features such as virtual geofencing and its information will act as enabler to create the data fusion infrastructure model that the SatisFactory ecosystem is aiming to deploy.

The Multiple-Media Manager will programmatically enrich localization data with visual information, especially to early trigger the incidents detection. Also other devices, like thermal cameras, will be considered as possible, non-intrusive privacy preserving instruments, in order to provide appropriate sources of data concerning workers' behaviours. Many operations will be performed through the real time analysis of the aforementioned data, preventing workers from going into potential dangerous areas (i.e. virtual geofencing), incorrect procedures or any other danger. The module in charge of handling these situations is the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager. It will analyse data coming from the Multi-Media Manager in order to guarantee a fast response and trigger safety mechanisms in reaction of safety related events, propagating ad-hoc messages to the Event Manager.

On the top of that, the context aware detection engine will provide two categories of safety approaches, namely *proactive* and *reactive*. The *proactive* actions can detect potential incident events (through real-time data analysis), while the *reactive* ones can detect incidents when they occur and as a consequence the corresponding predefined countermeasures are triggered.

Just to provide an example, a *proactive* measure can detect and alert a risky condition that might occur when a worker enters a forbidden/dangerous area. Therefore, this procedure is based on the

location of workers, the geometry of the plant and the geometry of the forbidden areas. The geometry of the forbidden areas can be set by the safety manager and changed any time. However, some dangerous area can be automatically set by the Context Manager module on the basis of particular events that may happen on the shop floor. For instance, some fire or explosions are detected from sensors whose positions are known. As a consequence, a dangerous area is automatically created on the basis of those sensors data. Thus, related alarm or escape procedures will be activated. The Context Manager will leverage on the Event Manager in order to simplify and harmonize the sharing of the safety related information among the SatisFactory platform.

Finally, the attention given to the security mechanisms, which is adopted by the intelligent IoT infrastructure over wireless networks, will ensure the integrity of the collected information and thereby guarantee accurate identification of risky scenarios which could compromise workers' safety.

8.3 *SCALABILITY PERSPECTIVE*

8.3.1 *Event Manager*

The LinkSmart middleware is capable of operating in P2P environments and one such example of deployment has been demonstrated in ALMANAC platform [ALMANAC] where real-time data from heterogeneous sensors and actuators are collected and processed to support Smart City processes. In SatisFactory, the Event Manager is used for two different communication patterns. First one is called client-to-centre pattern where physical layer components send messages to high level layers. In this pattern, the clients do not typically need to send messages to each other. The second pattern is a client-to-client pattern, where components of high-level layers (Facilities, Services etc.) send messages to each other. Given to this communication scenario and number of components, SatisFactory deployment is considered to be relatively small and Event Manager can easily handle communication among SatisFactory components. However, Event Manager can also employ "bridging" technique by forming a cluster of Event Managers to handle very large number of connected clients and messages.

8.3.2 *Semantic Framework*

The overall philosophy in architecting the Semantic Context Manager (SCM) is to provide a Web-based, scalable framework for integrating data and content from a variety of sources. The SCM corresponds to what is known as a Web-oriented architecture.

WOA builds on aspects of many of the largest properties on the Web, with proven scalability and extensibility. As used in SCM, these proven Web aspects are enhanced by adhering to open standards from the W3C (World Wide Web Consortium) in the areas of semantic technologies and vocabularies.

The SCM provides a standardized content storage and management environment that is Web-accessible, scalable and distributed. The content that can be hosted within the SCM includes documents (unstructured data), metadata (semi-structured data), conventional database information (structured data) and multimedia metadata. While this content can exist in multiple native formats in the wild, it is converted to the common RDF format that enables the development of standard ("canonical") tools and operations to act upon this content.

8.3.3 *Decision Support System*

The Integrated Decision Support System will incorporate and implement a number of different algorithms that will combine sensor data from various sources, context aware knowledge, production models and events and will finally produce a set of recommendations that may include actions over maintenance operations and schedules or worker activities, production re-adaptation, human resources workload management. The total architecture of the Integrated DSS (presented in section 4.2.2) allows handling increased workloads in order to provide the desired level of scalability by using both scale-up and scale-out techniques. Scale-up is the technique of increasing the available resources of the node that hosts the software application. The algorithms that will be running will be both computational-intensive and memory-intensive, so an increase in the number of available CPU cores and main system memory up to the physical limits of the HW in case a deterioration of the response time is monitored. This action will radically benefit the overall performance of the system and finally provide an acceptable level of scalability. If the limits of the HW are reached, then the system architecture, which is mainly Service Oriented, will provide us the ability to scale-out, meaning that we can add a number of new nodes hosting the services. Each new event or incident detected could trigger the execution of the appropriate recommendations providing algorithm in the less loaded node, with the help of a load balancer. This scale-out technique is feasible, due to the fact that the system does not need to internally hold the state of each request, meaning that subsequent requests for recommendations from the same source can be handled by different nodes. The result of the scale-out functionality will raise the scalability of the system in levels higher than those anticipated for the SatisFactory project.

8.4 *COMMUNICATION RELIABILITY PERSPECTIVE*

The physical-world interfacing and integration into the SatisFactory framework leverages on Wireless Sensor and Actuator Networks (WSANs). This system is expected to provide monitoring and control functions related to manufacturing environment. It will generate, collect and provide data related to people, machines and environment to the SatisFactory core components where these can be processed and exploited to enable context-aware functions. Typically, manufacturing environments are considered harsh for radio propagation, due to the availability of possibly large number of signal sources as well as the dense deployment of metallic objects. Moreover, different manufacturing scenarios and machinery operate under a variety of requirements with respect to the type and amount of collected data, and therefore, the WSANs are required to support these scenarios with the expected level of performance in order to adapt to the constraints derived from a wide range of applications. In this context, the dependability of the WSAN is strongly related to the dependability of its communication links.

Accordingly, SatisFactory WSANs are equipped with multi-radio communication capabilities, based on short-range wireless technologies such as IEEE 802.11 Wi-Fi, IEEE 802.15.1 Bluetooth, 802.15.4a UWB, and IEEE 802.15.4 6LoWPAN. Due to their different physical layer characteristics, complementary utilization of heterogeneous wireless technologies can suppress the weaknesses of individual radios, and thereby ensure a higher level of robustness. In addition, this would improve the WSAN flexibility and ability to support different application requirements in terms of the offered bandwidth, transmission latency, etc.

SatisFactory WSANs will feature multi-radio interface management leveraging a cognitive approach, by retrieving and monitoring networks' status and adaptively adjusting their configuration parameters. In addition, self-configuration and self-healing features will be supported by intelligent mechanisms to extend network availability and maintain end-to-end connectivity. Moreover, data reliability and integrity, in terms of correctness and timeliness, will be ensured exploiting cooperative mechanisms and secure communications.

9. TECHNICAL USE CASES INSTANTIATION

This section details some selected use cases by means of simple sequence diagrams to clarify how the SatisFactory platform behaves to deliver some specific features of interest. In particular, 10 UCs out of 21 have been chosen from D1.2 [SatisFactory D1.2], which are employed across several application scenarios such as:

- Reconfiguration of process flows and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures
- Recognition of incidents and path optimization for workers movement on the shop floor
- Preventive maintenance management system
- Manual assembly operations support
- Training platform for production process
- Online supervision of the operation and workforce resources of pilot plants
- Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction

The UCs selection for drawing the sequence diagrams have been performed in such a way the main components of the SatisFactory platform are employed at least in one of the selected UCs. The sequence diagrams related to the remaining UCs will be drawn in the next iteration of the architecture. In addition, the current presented sequence diagrams will be refined by taking into account inputs from WP3 and WP4 in the next iteration too.

The following subsections present the drawn sequence diagrams for the 10 selected UCs. The descriptions of the UCs have not been reported as they have been already presented in D1.2 [SatisFactory D1.2].

9.1 **UC1.2: STORAGE OF THE SHOP FLOOR INFORMATION AND DATA FROM THE MULTI-SENSORIAL NETWORKS**

Figure 23. UC1.2 Sequence Diagram.

9.2 **UC1.3: ANALYSIS OF REAL-TIME AND HISTORICAL INFO FROM SHOP FLOOR**

Figure 24. UC1.3 Sequence Diagram.

9-3 **UC2.1: IN-FACTORY TRAINING AND SUPPORT OF WORKERS USING A FLEXIBLE LEARNING PLATFORM**

Figure 25. UC2.1 Sequence Diagram.

9.4 UC2.2: VALIDATION OF TRAINING ACTIONS PERFORMED AT THE SHOP FLOOR

Figure 26. UC2.2 Sequence Diagram.

9.5 UC3.2: INCIDENT IDENTIFICATION BASED ON DYNAMIC EVOLVING OPERATIONS

Figure 27. UC3.2 Sequence Diagram.

9.6 **UC4.1: PROVIDE MAINTENANCE WORK PLANS AND ACTIONS RELATED TO HUMAN-CENTRIC ACTIVITIES**

Figure 28. UC4.1 Sequence Diagram.

9-7 UC4.3: MONITORING AND DECISION SUPPORT OF OPERATIONS & MAINTENANCE PROCEDURES

Figure 29. UC4.3 Sequence Diagram.

9.8 UC5.1: PLATFORM FOR SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

Figure 30. UC5.1 Sequence Diagram.

9.9 UC5.3: FUN CONTENT PLATFORM

Figure 31. UC5.3 Sequence Diagram.

9.10 UC6.3: KNOWLEDGE SHARING AMONG WORKERS BASED ON ADVANCED REASONING

Figure 32. UC6.3 Sequence Diagram.

10. CONCLUSIONS

This document included two main contributions from Task 2.1, the first one concerns the technology exploration, where both relevant EU funded projects and regional ones (in total 9) were analysed, while the second one concerns the definition of the SatisFactory architecture. We remind that two updated versions of the architecture are foreseen, one at M16 and a final one at M27.

The architecture was defined following three consecutive steps. In the first one, called *technology exploration*, relevant projects and technologies were analysed in order to identify critical aspects for the SatisFactory architecture that were taken into account in the next steps. In the second one, called *bottom-up* phase, a number of components and subcomponents, belonging to the set of partners' assets, were identified and considered necessary for the SatisFactory platform. In addition, missing components and corresponding functionalities were identified as well. Overall 11 main components and 38 subcomponents were collected. Each responsible partner presented the components' internal architecture, functionalities, and interaction with other main components. Following this approach, the SatisFactory architecture was defined and documented in three different views (namely, functional view, deployment view and information view) according to the standard IEEE 1471 "Recommended Practice for Architectural Description for Software-Intensive Systems" [IEEE 1471, 2000]. The third step, called *top-down* phase, was focused on each components role and their interaction. In particular, 10 use cases out of 21, identified within Task 1.3 [SatisFactory D1.2], were selected to build the related sequence diagrams by considering the identified components. This has allowed emphasizing the services each component would provide, and sketching the interactions between them. Finally, architectural perspectives were discussed to address quality properties and cross-cutting concerns such as satisfaction, safety and scalability.

REFERENCES

- [Adapt4ee] Adapt4EE, "Adapt4EE webpage." [Online]. Available: <http://www.adapt4ee.eu/adapt4ee/>. [Accessed: 16-Jul-2015].
- [Vehicle et al. 2014] V. Vehicle, T. Eu-commission, A. Tajani, V. Vehicle, W. C. Workspaces, S. Factories, E. Commission, S. Factory, S. Workers, S. Factory, and S. Factory, "1 st OFFICIAL PROJECT PRESS RELEASE Smart Factories: European research project focuses on the human component in tomorrow ' s production," 2014.
- [Facts4Workers] Facts4Workers, "FACTS4WORKERS Project." [Online]. Available: <http://facts4workers.eu/key-solutions/>. [Accessed: 15-Jul-2015].
- [mainDSS] mainDSS, "mainDSS Website." [Online]. Available: <http://www.maindss.eu/project.html>. [Accessed: 15-Jul-2015].
- [LinkedDesign 2015] P. LinkedDesign, "D10.8 The LinkedDesign Architecture - Second Update," 2015.
- [LinkedDesign 2012] P. LinkedDesign, "Linkeddesign Project Overview." pp. 1–7, 2012.
- [PlantCockPit webpage] P. PlantCockPit, "PlantCockpit: Motivation and Objectives." [Online]. Available: <http://plantcockpit.eu/index.php?id=410>. [Accessed: 16-Jul-2015].
- [PlantCockPit Architecture] A. PlantCockPit, "PlantCockpit: Architecture." [Online]. Available: <http://plantcockpit.eu/index.php?id=649>. [Accessed: 16-Jul-2015].
- [PlantCockPit Whitepaper] W. PlantCockPit, "PLANTCOCKPIT White Paper." [Online]. Available: http://plantcockpit.eu/fileadmin/PLANTCOCKPIT/user_upload/PLANTCockpit_D3.3_Public.pdf. [Accessed: 16-Jul-2015].
- [CoSpaces 2015] W. CoSpaces, "CoSpaces - Project Objectives." [Online]. Available: <http://www.cospaces.org/objectives.htm>. [Accessed: 16-Jul-2015].
- [Hardiman et al. 2010] S. Hardiman, V. C. D. Ampezzo, S. Hansen, U. Lang, and J. Wilson, Project Number 034245 D76 - Final publication of CoSpaces Reference Architecture Fraunhofer FIT, no. 034245. 2010.
- [APOSDLE webpage] H. APOSDLE, "APOSDLE learn@work." [Online]. Available: <http://www.aposdle.tugraz.at/>. [Accessed: 16-Jul-2015].
- [PROLIX 2015] W. PROLIX, "PROLIX." [Online]. Available: <http://www.prolixproject.org/>. [Accessed: 16-Jul-2015].
- [Mirror 2015] P. Mirror Webpage, "Mirror-Reflective Learning at work." [Online]. Available: <http://www.mirror-project.eu/>. [Accessed: 16-Jul-2015].
- [Mirror Deliverables]. D. Mirror, "Mirror Project Reports (Deliverables)." [Online]. Available: <http://www.mirror-project.eu/research-results/deliverables>. [Accessed: 16-Jul-2015].
- [Adapt4EE D2.1] D. Adapt4EE D2.1, "D2.1 Adapt4EE Conceptual Architecture."
- [Jimeno et al.] J. Jimeno, N. Ruiz, T. Tryferidis, D. Tzovaras, and K. Tsatsakis, "Framework for the Integration of Active Tertiary Prosumers into a Smart Distribution Grid," inertia-project.eu.

[Kostelnik et al. 2011] P. Kostelnik, M. Sarnovsk, and K. Furdik, "The semantic middleware for networked embedded systems applied in the Internet of Things and Services domain," Scalable Comput. Pract., 2011.

[ebbits] <http://www.ebbits-project.eu/>. [Accessed: 30-Jul-2015].

[Brizzi et al. 2013] Brizzi, P.; Conzon, D.; Khaleel, H.; Tomasi, R.; Pastrone, C.; Spirito, A.M.; Knechtel, M.; Pramudianto, F.; Cultrona, P., "Bringing the Internet of Things along the manufacturing line: A case study in controlling industrial robot and monitoring energy consumption remotely," *Emerging Technologies & Factory Automation (ETFA), 2013 IEEE 18th Conference on*, vol., no., pp.1,8, 10-13 Sept. 2013.

[Satisfactory D1.1] Satisfactory consortium, "User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and deployment guidelines", delivered at M4, April 2015.

[Satisfactory D1.2] Satisfactory consortium, "Use Case analysis and application scenarios description" delivered at M7, July 2015.

[IEEE1471, 2000] IEEE Standard 1471-2000 (2000), IEEE Recommended Practice for Architectural Description of Software-Intensive Systems.

[Hydra] Hydra "Hydra Middleware webpage." [Online]. Available: <http://www.hydramiddleware.eu/>. [Accessed: 29-Jul-2015].

[Al-Akkad et al., 2009] Al-Akkad, A., Pramudianto, F., Jahn, M., Zimmermann, A. (2009): "Middleware for building pervasive systems". International Association for Development of the Information Society (IADIS): International Conference Applied Computing, Rome, pages 1–8

[Eikerling et.al, 2009] Eikerling, H., Gräfe, G., Röhr, F., Schneider, W. (2009), "Ambient Healthcare-Using the Hydra Embedded Middleware for Implementing an Ambient Disease Management System". In Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Health Informatics, Portugal, pages 82–89.

[Jahn et al., 2010] Jahn, M., Jentsch, M., Prause, C. R., Pramudianto, F., Al-Akkad, A., Reiners, R. (2010). „The Energy Aware Smart Home". In 2010 5th International Conference on Future Information Technology, pages 1–8

[Reiners et al., 2009] Reiners, R., Zimmermann, A., Jentsch, M., Zhang, Y. (2009). Automizing home environments and supervising patients at home with the hydra middleware: application scenarios using the hydra middleware for embedded systems".CASTA '09 - Proceedings of the first international workshop on Context-aware software technology and applications, pages 9-12

[ALMANAC] ALMANAC "ALMANAC webpage." [Online]. Available: <http://www.almanac-project.eu/>. [Accessed: 29-Jul-2015].

[IoT-A D1.2] IoT-A consortium, "Initial architectural reference model for the IoT". (<http://www.iot-a.eu/public/public-documents/d1.2/view>). [Accessed: 03-Aug-2015].

ANNEX 1 – SATISFACTORY RELEVANT PROJECTS

A1.1 *FACTS4WORKERS*

Production is moving constantly away from European high-wage countries to so-called “best-cost” countries or to locations with low energy cost. To fight this trend the European industry is challenged to develop intelligent added-value concepts for the field of production.

Over the idea “Improved training and increase of investment in factories will help bring Europe new and better jobs”; FACTS4WORKERS puts the worker into to the centre of future-oriented production concepts in order to render manufacturing jobs more attractive and help Europe to become more competitive [Vehicle et al. 2014].

Goal of the project:

The goals of the project, address to three different fields: Research, Smart Factory and The human component; they are described below [Vehicle et al. 2014].

Research:

The project initiates a new industrial era, which is characterized by the so-called “Smart Factory”. The “Smart Workers” in those production sites are ideally supported by information and communication technology in order to improve the manufacturing process regarding flexibility, efficiency, and reliability. This results in a local benefit in competition, and (central) European production locations can be secured in the long term.

Smart Factory:

In a “Smart Factory”, the production site of the future, the focus lies on the worker as the most flexible element involved in the manufacturing process. The worker becomes a “production knowledge worker” and is supported by optimized information and communication technology, self-learning working environment, and in-situ learning while operating the machine. The digitalisation is not just to factories; it will affect entire added value networks. This is achieved via systems consisting of various components (IT, software, mechanical parts, etc.) that communicate via the internet or other means of communication.

The human component:

In terms of “Smart Factory”, there also has to be a focus on the role of the worker as the human component and key factor in the manufacturing process. Here there is a new concept, “knowledge work”, which is defined by an entirely new, complex, and autonomous work environment. Furthermore, “Smart Workers” develop new ways of continuous improvement of knowledge exchange on their own at the work place. The objective is to understand, how people work and learn, how they interact with new technologies, and how they can create an added value to the industry by working at an attractive and demanding work place. The answers to these questions are the key to successful and human-centred solutions of information and communication strategies

within manufacturing processes. Increasing satisfaction and motivation, the productivity will increase by 10 per cent.

Related architectures:

The overall architecture is shown in Figure 33 below.

Figure 33: Overall FACT4WORKERS Architecture [Facts4Workers].

The proposed solution is a worker-centric smart factory, satisfying the workers’ goals. FACTS4WORKERS develops a modular smart factory infrastructure, interlinking a number of building blocks, described as follows [Facts4Workers]:

- **SmartWorker-Centric HCI/HMI building blocks:** It provides workers with novel ways to interact with information and knowledge inside the working environment adopting the latest devices.
- **Worker Centric Service Building Blocks:** It provides the content for the selected worker-interface, unfolding the treasure of manufacturing data, information and knowledge to the worker via APIs.
- **Smart Factory Infrastructure:** It is the back-end infrastructure including the latest developments in data enrichment and aggregation, including semantics and linked data, datafication and analytics, and visualisation frameworks.

Smart Factory Data: It is the hidden “treasure” to be unfolded by our developed technologies and services, ranging from multiple data sources and data formats.

A1.2 MAINDSS

The mainDSS project focuses on the necessity of maintenance. Consultants and experts always would like to extract sound information from the corporate Computerised Maintenance Management System (CMMS) in order to assess maintenance data, records, etc. and then apply criteria and performance indicators, combining them with their expertise and experience, and conclude into their recommendations and audit reports for the management. The project developed an IT system to be used by industries themselves as a plug-in approach to interface with CMMS repositories.

Goal of the project:

Nowadays, in competitive business environment one of the key challenges is to maximize the operational availability of assets and minimize the life-cycle costs. Maintenance offers significant opportunities in reducing cost and increasing production outcome, being a good choice to improve the competitive business environment. However, it is considered as a “black hole” where costs are generated without having straightforward ways of measuring returns; industries have to address three main problems [mainDSS]:

1. Lack of an effective communication between managerial and technical departments. Management executives are unfamiliar with the required concepts for understanding life cycle maintenance needs (targets to set, KPIs to measure) and assessing the impact of long-term maintenance investments.
2. Maintenance teams focus on repair-maintenance, instead of establishing a proactive-oriented maintenance department and prioritizing the necessary maintenance pillars. Usually the enterprises use support from maintenance consultants, but they are often unaffordable, especially for industrial Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs).
3. CMMS platforms focus on day to day maintenance performance and neglect holistic assessment of maintenance department performance; there are not any effective suggestions for improvements or means to comparatively assess the performance of the industry.

In order to solve these problems, mainDSS offers a plug-in approach, which dynamically makes a bridge with CMMS repositories and retrieving all necessary data in order to know, the current maintenance performance of the company.

Related architectures:

The overall mainDSS architecture is shown in Figure 34 below:

Figure 34: Overall mainDSS Architecture [mainDSS].

- **Maintenance ontology:** It is used to model infrastructure components (e.g. assets), CMMS model entities (e.g. Bill of Materials) and common maintenance operations (MTBF & equipment replacement). The ontology represents concepts (e.g. MTTR) and their relationships, and facilitates applied operations.
- **Auditing module:** It is responsible for the management of various auditing criteria and the persistent storage and retrieval of auditing results; it is used to assess effectiveness of maintenance operations by asking if the spare parts with stock level are below the established minimum, if the MTTR is too high or the consolidated cost of a machine failure. It provides to the management the financial and quality reports based on best practices and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) compliant to international standards; complimented by a Progress Control module to monitor the progress of the maintenance department (i.e. comparative assessment of current and historical data, at selected time periods).

The specific tasks that the module is responsible for are the following:

- Provision of user interfaces that give the ability to the end user to define auditing criteria, along with an interface to manage them (e.g. edit an existing criterion, add a new one, etc.), to save/reload them, etc.
- Implementation of repository mechanisms that store and retrieve auditing results, per company and period of time.
- **Decision Support (DSS) module:** It provides recommendations and defines priorities for leveraging maintenance performance and offering proposals for ameliorating identified shortcomings; for instance, if the MTBF is below the accepted threshold, then it may suggest increasing preventive maintenance, replacing equipment, training technicians or hiring more experienced technicians. This module is the point in the system where: visions, dimensions and

recommendations are managed, DSS engine rules and policies are configured and decision support engine runs in order to provide recommendations to the end users.

- **Bridging module:** Allows reliable import of data from CMMS repositories, this is the innovative plug-in approach. It is the link between the mainDSS auditing module and the client CMMS, Its main function is providing the information bridge between the two systems and controlling the way information flows. The primary user of the bridging module is the consultant implementing the mainDSS, which can perform the following tasks:
 - Configure various aspects of the plug-in that collects maintenance data
 - Configure details of the service and the interface
 - Configure the end-user alerts mechanism

A1.3 LINKEDDESIGN

LINKEDDESIGN project concentrates on the problem that it is not allowed to have an integrated, holistic view on data across the full product lifecycle for the current ICT landscape for manufacturing. Especially the design and engineering of products and manufacturing processes is decoupled from the actual process execution. A tight integration of all tools used throughout a product lifetime is usually not feasible, and this requires therefore new design methodologies and novel integration tools. The project provides a solution that allows the integration of the holistic view on data across the full product lifecycle for ICT.

Goal of the project:

LinkedDesign will boost the productivity of today's engineers by using the Linked Engineering and Manufacturing Platform (LEAP), capable of providing an integrated, holistic view on data, persons and processes across the product lifecycle as a vital resource for the outstanding competitive design of novel products and manufacturing processes.

LEAP is conceived as an integrated information system for manufacturing design. It merges all product lifecycle information relevant to drive engineering and manufacturing processes, independent of their format, location, originator, and time of creation. Besides the unified access to the integrated information, it provides specific knowledge exploitation solutions such as design decision support systems to analyse the integrated information.

In detail, LinkedDesign project provides User-centric lifecycle information management, Context-driven access to merged information and Knowledge and cross-discipline collaborations between users by novel approaches for collaborative engineering. In addition, it offers tight feedback connections to existing engineering tools in order to push back formalised knowledge to enable automated design of elementary product components.

Related architectures:

In Figure 35, it is shown, the overall- architecture, which is described in more detail in [LinkedDesign 2015].

All concepts and components developed have been evaluated using three application prototype focused on the following topics:

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- Manufacturing Design based on Plant Lifecycle Costs.
- Knowledge Re-use and Collaboration in Automated Design for Offshore Engineering.
- Metrology-driven Manufacturing in the Automobile Industry.

Figure 35: Overall LINKEDDESIGN Architecture [LinkedDesign 2012].

Some experimental results of using the LinkedDesign solution are the achieved estimated reductions of:

- Up to 50% in time spent for search and knowledge acquisition through the improved (collaborative) information access.
- Over 20% in time to market through support and automation of product and manufacturing design provided by the engineering platform.

The framework for knowledge exploitation within LinkedDesign has included:

1. Algorithms for the product and plant lifecycle data analysis that are applied in a decision support system to optimize the design of products/processes.
2. Algorithms of the statistical analysis to correlate errors detected with the 3D metrology with corresponding process configurations.
3. Algorithms for customer opinion mining that incorporate domain expert knowledge provided by the LinkedDesign Knowledge Network.

The algorithms could be considered as machine learning that automatically recognizes complex patterns and makes intelligent decisions based on the given data. However, LinkedDesign scenarios involve engineers, manufacturers or other users as essential stakeholders. The solution does not target pure machine learning algorithms based on artificial intelligence, but goes for decision support systems that analyse and process the given data and expose a set of high-quality solutions to the user.

A1.4 PLANTCOCKPIT

The Factories of the Future Public-Private Partnership (FoFPPP) initiative aims at helping EU manufacturing enterprises, in particular SMEs, to adapt to global competitive pressures by developing the necessary key enabling technologies across a broad range of sectors. It will help European industry to meet increasing global consumer demand for greener, more customized and higher quality products through the necessary transition to a demand-driven industry with less wastage and a better use of resources. In order to contribute to the FoFPPP initiative, this project develops a central environment for monitoring and controlling of all intra-logistical processes. PLANTCockpit provides production supervisors, foremen, and line managers with the required visibility to make well-informed decisions for optimizing plant processes [PlantCockPit webpage].

Goals of the project:

These days, numerous methods, systems, and tools exist to facilitate production management, optimize resource utilization, and process efficiency. However, current Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES), Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA), and special-purpose solutions are rarely integrated with each other and typically provide no more than point-to-point interfaces between selected functionalities [PlantCockPit webpage].

The sporadic point-to-point integrations do not fulfil the requirements of today's dynamic markets where enterprises have to quickly judge complex situations, react to unexpected events, and make far-reaching decisions. With the growing focus on sustainability, complexity grows even further as production supervisors have to manage energy and material consumption, carbon footprint, and waste output in addition to classical KPIs like process efficiency, asset utilization, quality, scrap rate, and costs. Efforts to find the optimum for yield, quality, speed, or energy consumption often result in local optima, far from the ideal solution. Optimization must start at global bottlenecks within the plant or supply network, which can only be identified if overall process transparency is given. Only a tight integration of all systems will provide the visibility and process integration needed to truly recognize the potentials and optimize intra-logistics processes; be it with respect to yield, quality, energy consumption, or waste [PlantCockPit webpage].

PLANTCockpit is a central environment for monitoring and control of all intra-logistical processes. The outputs will help production supervisors, foremen, and line managers with the required visibility to make well-informed decisions to optimise plant processes. In order to do that, it includes the holistic visibility of the plan, the current status, deviations, exceptions, and bottlenecks. PLANTCockpit suggests a model for integrating heterogeneous shop floor management systems including ERP, MES, SCADA, condition-based maintenance, energy management, and other special-purpose systems. Virtually all manufacturing operations are multi-vendor environments which makes a harmonization of all systems a highly challenging goal. PLANTCockpit focuses on defining standard interfaces and a reference model for integrating the most prominent manufacturing processes. Current shop floor integration standards such as ISA 95, OAGIS, OPC Unified Architecture, MTConnect will be used as starting points.

The following are the main goals of the PLANTCockpit project with their respective activities to achieve them [PlantCockPit webpage]:

1. Visibility and integration across all manufacturing processes, layers, and systems:

- a. Manufacturing ontology, data and process model
- b. Standardised interfaces
- c. Flexible information integration and process orchestration
- d. Propagation and aggregation of alarms and events
- e. Visual integration

2. Optimized production and logistics processes:

- a. Data gathering and bottleneck determination
- b. Optimization through simulation and advanced planning

3. Increased energy efficiency and reduced waste production:

- a. Monitoring
- b. Contextualized analysis
- c. Asset optimization through intelligent maintenance

Related Architectures:

Figure 36 presents the PLANTCockpit architecture. The architecture is done adopting the layer-based concept, in order to separate different functional aspects and facilitate customization and configuration. It allows the use of different technologies for the implementation, provides easy extensibility for new functionalities, focuses on the major functional aspects concerning production and logistic cockpits and it is driven by the user requirements.

Figure 36: Overall PLANTCockpit Architecture [PlantCockPit Architecture].

The connection between the layers and different components is provided by message-based uniform and standardized interfaces. Each layer provides various functional components with specific functionalities and connections between them. All the layers and their inner components are described in detail in [PlantCockPit Whitepaper].

A1.5 COSPACES

Ambient Interfaces and ubiquitous computing are characterised by the integration of the increasingly complex technological landscape with human environment, while removing the perception of the computer in the tasks and activities that are undertaken. The evolution of IT over the last decades has led to the development of individual CAD/ CAE workstations. While the computational power available to Engineering professionals has grown exponentially, the collaborative dimension of the workspace has been largely under developed. CoSpaces provides an evolutionary path towards new and more collaborative work environments. The users of CoSpaces technologies in manufacturing and design, working in cooperation with their suppliers, are able to configure their own collaborative workspaces and utilise ground-breaking innovations in context-aware interfaces, natural interfaces, and “human-centric” workspaces supporting a range of collaboration scenarios and product lifecycles. The developed platform supports product design and manufacturing in geographically dispersed teams in distributed virtual engineering

enterprises. It helps the team members to participate in decision-making, view designs, propose modifications, and access reference material in ways that are specific to their disciplines, and allow them to interact using a range of devices depending on their current location and situation [CoSpaces 2015].

Goal of the project:

The CoSpaces project has evaluated collaboration at individual, team and enterprise levels, and developed collaboration models emphasizing applications of problem solving, creativity, participatory and knowledge based design in innovative collaborative work environments. CoSpaces is a distributed software framework that supports easy creation of collaborative work environments for distributed knowledge workers and teams in collaborative design and engineering tasks.

CoSpaces features a collaborative platform for viewing a workspace. Several experts have a domain specific view on the workspace at the same time. This enables them to discuss topics together. Also augmented reality technology is integrated into the platform. It allows experts to experience the workspace from the viewpoint of an end-user already during the design phase.

The CoSpaces project addresses the following objectives [CoSpaces 2015]:

- Evaluate collaboration at individual, team and enterprise levels, and develop collaboration models emphasizing applications of problem solving, creativity, participatory and knowledge based design in innovative collaborative work environments.
- Create an innovative distributed software framework that will support easy creation of collaborative work environments for distributed knowledge workers and teams in collaborative design and engineering tasks.
- Validate the distributed software framework for creating different classes of collaborative working styles required for collaborative design and engineering in the Aerospace, Automotive and Construction sectors.

Related architectures:

The CoSpaces application components are illustrated in Figure 37.

Figure 37: Application Components [Hardiman et al. 2010].

- **Portal:** It is the interface to the users. Its backend, the Collaboration Broker (CB) communicates with the other framework components and processes data and input from and for the user.
- **The Dynamic Session Management (DSM):** It is responsible for the dynamic parts of the collaboration, i.e., meetings.
- **Group Management, Knowledge Support, Positioning and Identification:** They provide various kinds of information, which is required during the collaboration.
- **Resource Management (RM):** It is responsible for the availability of data to the users.
- **Application Controller (AC):** It manages the applications during a meeting and the communication between them.

In a corporate enterprise architecture, the purpose of an application portfolio catalogue is to identify and maintain a list of all the applications in the enterprise. The current application model for CoSpaces is depicted in Figure 38.

Figure 38: Application Portfolio Catalogue [Hardiman et al. 2010].

A1.6 *MIRROR*

Overall Objective of “MIRROR” is to develop a **personal performance mirroring and improvement solution**. MIRROR combines instruments of personal competency and potential analysis, reflection, interaction and learning based on activities within a work process. MIRROR helps to identify improvement potentials of oneself to increase the productivity and business performance. Benchmarking with a peer group within a social network is in the core of MIRROR. People who share the same work experience and job roles can use MIRROR across companies for temporary or

continuous personal improvement and learning support. By this, MIRROR integrates personal learning with personal improvement strategies and performance management [Mirror 2015].

From a technological perspective, MIRROR will offer instruments and tools to log and track personal business activities and compare the activities with other peers in a social network. For activity tracking, MIRROR uses tools on the desktop as well as on mobile tracking devices. The tools build on results of APOSDLE [APOSDLE webpage] for activity tracking and of PROLIX [PROLIX 2015] for matching people competencies as well as analysis of competency gaps. MIRROR will provide a personal visual desk board for training planning, gap analysis, benchmarking, performance comparison etc. MIRROR will use semantic technologies for competencies and learning to analyse business activities, to match profiles of people with working attitudes and to bring all this into a social network of people with same interests and roles in business. MIRROR will also provide game elements for learning in the group within the social network.

The Idea behind the project is that the motivation to learn in business is highly related to individual objectives and how people see themselves in comparison to others in the same work environment or job role. On the job-training with technologies is still a very new method, there are yet not enough learning and creativity tools that support learning at the work place in a systematic way. In Sports-Training, systematic analysis of time spend to train – related with a goal to reach, collecting data like time, pulse frequency, speed, etc. allows to measure and benchmark the training success and get fitness data. MIRROR transfers this approach into a business environment for training and learning by self-reflection.

Training and learning from others means to learn from them by knowing how they act, what they do, how they do it compared to oneself. With MIRROR people will see how they can change their working style, knowledge and competencies in order to be better and more productive in business and for their own company. MIRROR will be a personal system, so data will be only accessible for oneself, if allowed for others in an anonymous way; it is not a managed environment from a company for the employees. MIRROR can be used for example in the following scenarios:

- Sales professionals in the automobile industry can find out, how other sales professionals work, what they know, how they structure their working days, how much time they spend for their activities etc. Based on this, MIRROR will allow creating groups of people with the same working profile and providing learning recommendations and coaching service to improve the group.
- Shop floor personal in the retail business can capture over a time of 3-6 weeks every activity in detail. The data will be aggregated and made comparable with others in the same business. Graphical activity charts will show, how the own business day is being structured and compared to others. Based on these data, individual recommendations for changes in the attitude of work, timing, knowledge, etc. will be given by the system.

Related architectures:

An overview of the Mirror architecture is shown in Figure 39 below.

Figure 39: First Overview of the MIRROR Architecture [Mirror Deliverables].

A1.7 ADAPT₄EE

Adapt₄EE aims to develop and validate a holistic energy performance evaluation framework that incorporates architectural metadata (i.e., BIM), critical business processes (i.e., BPM) and consequent occupant behaviour patterns, enterprise assets and respective operations as well as overall environmental conditions. The Adapt₄EE framework, having as a central point of reference the occupancy behaviour (presence and movement) aligns energy consumption points to all interrelated enterprise aspects (business processes, enterprise assets and utility state and operations) [Adapt₄ee].

In this context, Adapt₄EE developed an enhanced semantic enterprise model that treats, learns and manages the enterprise environment as an intelligent agent, perceives environmental state using multi-type sensors and information modalities. The Adapt₄EE Model incorporates business processes and occupancy data. It also constitutes a formal model for enterprise energy performance measuring, monitoring and optimization. The model is calibrated during the training phase based on sensor data captured during operation and then applied and evaluated in real-life every day enterprise operations. More specifically the Adapt₄EE Enterprise Models allows for the proactive identification of optimum local adaptations of enterprise utility operations, based on predictions of possible occupancy patterns and respective business operations and energy profiles. To this end, Adapt₄EE provides a set of Open Business Reference Models as well as respective methods and tools for modelling and simulating the real life operation of construction products, thus allowing for more accurate and realistic evaluation of the energy impact of alternative design and planning decision at an early design phase, prior to realization.

Related architectures:

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The overall Adapt4EE conceptual architecture is comprised of two main frameworks, the measurement and the simulation framework [Adapt4EE D2.1], which are visually depicted in Figure 40 and Figure 41.

Figure 40 : Adapt4EE Measurement Framework [Adapt4EE D2.1].

Figure 41 : Adapt4EE Simulation Framework [Adapt4EE D2.1].

- The agent-training module: It is fed with semantically enriched information gathered by the Adapt4EE Middleware and it is able to analyse the actual building space utilization having as main catalyst the occupants (presence and flows).

Simulation Framework:

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- Occupancy prediction module: It is responsible for predicting the occupancy of a building and its space utilizing the occupancy information from the measurement framework and the building information.
- Agent-based simulation module: It processes and controls the generation of simulated space utilization of the building, taking into account the business processes occurring in the specific enterprise, the user behaviour modelling (as provided by the Occupancy Prediction Module) and the current space layout (i.e., BIM).
- User Activity Simulation Module: It incorporates the information from the Agent-based Simulation Module and from the Occupancy Prediction Module, and generates a spatiotemporal model of building space utilization by users.
- Building performance simulation module: The extracted detailed occupancy schedule for the building spaces (multi-agent based activity building simulation) along with the enterprise energy profile models feed the Building Performance Simulation Module, that is able to estimate the energy performance of the building taking into account both the architectural envelope itself and the facility users and the activities performed by them.

Visual analytics module: It implements different energy-related views of the building under design and provides the capability to compare and assess the energy efficiency of multiple design alternatives.

A1.8 INERTIA

INERTIA adopts the Internet of Things/Services principles to the Distribution Grid Control Operations. Semantically enhanced DER will be the main constituents of the INERTIA active distribution grid management framework. They will constitute active and flexible components (generation as well as consumption) that carry contextual knowledge concerning their local environment. Within INERTIA, DER will form dynamic clusters that essentially comprise self-organized networks of intelligent active nodes that will efficiently distribute and balance global and local intelligence. This self-organized overlay network of connected DER will allow for the seamless management and control of the active grid as well as the efficient coordination and exploration of single and aggregated technical prosumer potential (generation and consumption) to participate in energy balancing and other distributed grid related services.

Global Operational and Technical parameters of the electricity grid will be seamlessly and continuously translated into real-time Local Control Strategies. INERTIA will offer fine grained control (equivalent or even higher than existing Direct Control Programmes) while at the same time ensure privacy and autonomy on the local level, fully respecting prosumer preferences and needs. INERTIA will promote the efficient integration of flexible demand with distributed generation within the smart grid as the means to tackle the problems resulting from the continuous and massive integration of distributed intermittent and non-controllable renewable sources

More specifically, the main objectives of INERTIA are the following:

- **Objective 1**: Innovative DSM framework, for the efficient integration of local demand and generation (DER) to the smart grid and utilization of DER flexibility for the optimal coordination of the Distribution Grid.

- **Objective 2:** Semantically Enhanced and Multi-Dimensional DER (Generation and Consumption) Profiles.
- **Objective 3:** Integrated Prosumer Profiles, Incorporating Behaviour, Activity Flows and Environmental Knowledge.
- **Objective 4:** Multi-Agent Based Distributed Grid Management Framework.
- **Objective 5:** Multi-Directional Communication and Control Framework for Horizontal and Vertical Integration of Active Components (DER).
- **Objective 6:** Holistic Energy Performance Models and Respective Business/Contractual Models for the S&M Cis.

Related architectures:

The overall INERTIA conceptual architecture is depicted in Figure 42 and presented in the paper [Jimeno et al.] The INERTIA control network on the highest level will consist of two types of peers/“Hubs”, while appropriate intelligent agents will be running on both hubs, underlying the self-organized distributed grid and load control operations:

- **Local Control Hub:** Corresponding to the level of building areas, buildings or building complexes, the Local Control Hub will autonomously and automatically manage in real-time local control actions and respective information.
- **Aggregator Hub:** Through this Hub the Aggregators will be provided with real-time monitoring and control tools, in order to efficiently organize their customer loads portfolio and define specific Active Demand strategies and respective services based on market needs, acting as an intermediary between suppliers, network operators and prosumers belonging to their portfolios.

Figure 42: INERTIA Conceptual Architecture [Jimeno et al.].

The main components of the INERTIA framework are described below:

Local Control Hub:

- Semantically Based Middleware: It provides a multi-directional communication and control interface of individual and aggregated DERs (local loads and generation) with the Distribution Grid.
- Occupancy Flow Modelling and Prediction: It is responsible for extracting real-time building occupancy flows based on data stemming from the multi-sensorial cloud, as well as for occupancy modelling and prediction.
- DER Flexibility Modelling: It provides integrated models, extending the typical two dimensional stochastic profiles in an attempt to deliver Context Aware Multi-Dimensional Load Flexibility Profiles.
- User Profiling: It monitors and learns transparently occupants' behaviour, in order to extract user preference models.
- Performance Modelling: It models and calculates the necessary parameters (KPIs) contributing to the Holistic Flexibility decision making.
- Holistic Flexibility Analysis, Aggregation and Forecasting: It has the responsibility of determining the control strategy which should be applied by analysing and correlating data coming from other internal frameworks.
- Building Monitoring and Control: It is responsible for monitoring building operation and applying control strategies.
- Ambient User Interface: Personalized Ambient User Interfaces will be developed in order to address final occupants' and facility managers' needs.

Aggregator Control Hub:

- DER Flexibility Analysis, Aggregation and Forecasting: It provides visualization and interaction mechanisms to the Aggregator for multidimensional analysis, correlation and efficient management of prosumer profiles.
- Grid Coordination and Demand Response Activation: It is the communication interface between the Aggregator Control Hub and the DSO system.
- Multi-Agent Based DER Prosumers Control and Optimization: It ensures the efficient execution of Global Demand Control Strategies through coordinated, distributed local control actions on selected clusters of the aggregator's portfolio.

Common Aspects:

Common Information Model (CIM): It defines the high level domain model/ontology comprising the basic elements underlying the INERTIA framework

A1.9 EBBITS

The ebbits project provides semantic approach to IoT and hence introduces an innovative bridge between backend enterprise applications, people, services and the physical world, using information generated by tags, sensors, and other devices and performing actions on the real world. The ebbits platform enables these main innovative features:

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- *Semantic interoperability* between heterogeneous physical world technologies and the enterprise systems, also outlining scalable network architectures and featuring opportunistic communication paradigms.
- *IoT entity Virtualization*, through an addressing layer based on unique identifiers, it enables discovery features, through semantic techniques and attribute-based services descriptions.
- *Innovative Data and Event Management*, through a P2P (peer-to-peer) Event Management Architecture, which leverages on the publish/subscribe communication paradigm to handle rule-based service orchestration.
- *Centralized and Distributed Intelligence*, which allows the definition of data fusion frameworks and adopting ontology-based context models to promote self-awareness mechanisms.
- *Semantic Knowledge Infrastructure*, connecting many conventional data sources to semantic models, with support of hybrid querying and real-time reasoning.
- Support for Business Process Life Cycle Management, including process taxonomy and optimization metrics.

Related architecture

The ebbits project advances the LinkSmart middleware³, the main result of an EU project called Hydra. It combines a service-oriented architecture, peer-to-peer networking technologies and semantic Web Services, addressing the interoperability issue. On the top of LinkSmart, the ebbits platform builds its five main layers (as depicted in the overall architecture diagram in Figure 43):

- *Physical World layer*: includes real-world devices (e.g. robot controller, PLCs, energy measuring sensors, WSANs), which are accessible via proper drivers and adapters. The key component at this layer is the Physical-World Adaptation Layer (PWAL), and adaptation component responsible for exposing device resources and data access capabilities in a unified way.
- *Internet of Things layer*: offers “Thing” enabling functionality needed for IoT resource management, including resource discovery provided by Internet of Service Layer. Key components are based on the LinkSmart middleware.
- *Internet of Services layer*: provides services and resource catalogue functionality, as well as event processing capabilities. Key components at this layer are the IoT Service Manager, Event Processing Agent, and Thing Discovery Manager.
- *Business System Mediation layer*: provide interfaces for applications and enterprise systems and offers the abstractions of things, services and people for IoT enabled applications. Key components are Thing Manager, People Manager, Context Manager and Service Proxy.
- *Inter Business layer*: is the highest layer of the ebbits platform architecture focused on support traceability and information management for IoT enabled entities, such as products or different types of physical goods. Key component is Product Service

³ <https://linksmart.eu>

Orchestration Manager that resolves and invokes services in order to assemble a product life cycle.

Orthogonal to the identified layers are components that offer infrastructure functionality, such as the Network, Security and Opportunistic Manager. In addition, the Ontology Manager implements a semantic model to collect information regarding devices, services, events, as well as obtaining knowledge supporting the ebbits decision-making components, such as the Context Manager.

Main ebbits platform components

The ebbits platform architecture is composed by several system modules, each one with specific functionalities is briefly presented in [Kostelnik et al. 2011; Brizzi et al. 2013]. The main components are:

- *Network Manager*: this component is the entry and exit point of the LinkSmart middleware. There must be only one instance of it, in every device, where the middleware is running. This component provides the entry point of the middleware as a Web Service interface. Furthermore, it creates the overlay P2P network needed to interconnect the components of the middleware. It provides the architecture needed to address LinkSmart Web Services using unique IDs and it provides the transport mechanism over the P2P network, needed to invoke the LinkSmart Web Services (SOAP Tunnelling) using their IDs.

Figure 43. ebbits Architecture [ebbts].

- Event Manager*: it is the component used to implement the publish/subscribe paradigm on the top of the functionalities provided by the LinkSmart middleware. It provides an application-level selected multicast that decouples senders and receivers in time, space, and data (i.e., sender and receivers do not need to be up at the same time, do not need to know each other's network addresses and do not need to use the same data schema for events they send). It leverages the JXTA Pipe Abstraction, which provides a virtual connection between two pipes' endpoints: the input pipe and output one. Pipe connections are independent from pipe location and connectivity, thus enabling to bypass network issues like firewall or NAT. Publish-subscribe mechanism is implemented through JXTA since a pipe endpoint can subscribe to messages sent from a publisher endpoint. Using this manager, the developers can create applications based on asynchronous events; the Event Manager can be used both to send events and to subscribe itself to the topic of interest.

- *Ontology Manager*: the purpose of this component is to provide a unified interface for using the LinkSmart Device Ontology and all related modules, within the LinkSmart middleware. The manager maintains run-time instances of the LinkSmart devices.
- *Context Manager*: a unified interface to access the context of entities in the environment, it decouples the application from the context providers (sensors), which consequently eases the application developer tasks. The context management consists of an Entity Manager and Rule Manager, both depending on the Event Manager to retrieve sensor data from the proxies.
- *Entity Manager*: exploits the Ontology Manager to retrieve the metadata of the sensor readings, such as location, measurement unit, reading interval, and other attributes. This manager is responsible to store the current context attributes of the entities. For this purpose, the developers must define which entities and context attributes are to be monitored by the Context Manager. The application developers can define this in the header of the rules, which then are passed to the rule engine. In this way, the Entity Manager can monitor only the state of the system that is needed, optimizing the performance of the Context Manager.
- *Rule Manager*: The Context Manager recognizes situational context based on rules defined by the developers and stored by the Rule Manager component. The rules may also define a higher level of context information, which must be inferred based on several sensor information, and their semantics defined by the ontology. In the rules, there is also the definition of action that should be performed when certain context is recognized.
- *Physical World Adaption Layer (PWAL)*: The PWAL is the adaption layer between the Physical World sensors and Internet of Things platform, used to provide a common way to interconnect physical entities (including sensors, devices, protocols and communication channels), which are not part of LinkSmart or of other ebbits components. The main role of the PWAL is to abstract any device connected to the platform, exposing its capabilities and output data and hiding the specific implementation details (hardware and software). Specifically, the capabilities exposed are the events generated, the services offered and the direct access to information stored into hardware resources. In this way, the application that uses the device can interact with it, without knowing details about its implementation. The capabilities of the device are exposed through the PWAL driver, which provides, on one side, an abstraction to the device specific technologies and, on the other side, a uniform interface for other ebbits components, ensuring that devices can be integrated seamlessly with the other IoT components of the platform.

ANNEX 2 – SUB-COMPONENTS DESCRIPTION

Sub-component Name

Dependable Network Infrastructure

Description

This component comprises wireless networks of IoT devices, featuring robust connectivity for delivering relevant data and events across the shop floor. This component is essential for providing the necessary information to the SatisFactory knowledge-base and thereby enable context-aware applications.

Services

- Robust wireless connectivity
- Secure communications
- Complex network management

Dependencies

- Automation Systems - I/O Field Network
- Ultra Wide Band (UWB) Localization Devices
- Depth Sensor Network
- Thermal Sensor Network
- Device Manager
- Event Manager

Inputs needed

- Factory layout according to the use-case definition
- System architecture
- End-user requirements
- Technical requirements

Outputs provided

- Dependable communication API
- Physical-world monitoring and control API

Related Tasks

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- T4.1: Development of intelligent IoT infrastructure to enable context-aware applications
- T4.2: Hardware Development of context-aware HMIs
- T4.4: Development of intelligent notification and control middleware
- T4.5: Integration of social collaboration and sensing environments for enhancing collective awareness

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Physical Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

REST APIs

Sub-component Name

Ultra Wide Band (UWB) Wearable Devices

Description

The UWB Wearable Devices can be of three types (i.e., tag, anchor and gateway) and are used in indoor environments to provide location information. Typically, the anchors are placed in fixed and well know positions in the region of interest. The tags are worn by workers and/or installed on mobile objects whose positions need to be estimated. During the estimation process the tags continuously interact with anchors. In particular, each tag performs range measurements with respect to the anchors that are in the connectivity range. After that, a localization algorithm, which runs on the tag itself, uses range measurements and anchor positions to estimate the tag's position. Finally, the gateway is the end-point of the localization devices; it receives localization data from tags and forwards them to the Localization Manager through the Middleware by using a serial interface.

Services

- Location information
- Ranging information

Dependencies

- Middleware
- Localization Manager

Inputs needed

- Coordinates of UWB anchors
- Ids of anchors
- Localization update rate

Outputs provided

- Ranging data (distance between tag and anchor, tag Id and anchor Id)
- Localization data (tag Id, flag position estimated, estimated coordinates expressed according to a relative reference system, number of ranging measurements, anchor connectivity, localization accuracy)

Related Tasks

- Task 3.3: Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort
- T4.1: Development of intelligent IoT infrastructure to enable context-aware applications

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Physical Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

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- At tag level: UWB-based messages
- At gateway level: serial messages

Sub-component Name

Depth Sensor Network

Description

The depth sensor network is responsible for providing the system privacy preserving information from depth cameras/sensors to the system. This information will be mainly focused on the analysis of the human movements and actions in the shop floor.

Services

- Acquisition of human movements/actions in the shop floor

Dependencies

- Middleware
- Incident detection tool

Inputs needed

- No input needed

Outputs provided

- Trace of the detected humans in the shop floor
- Trajectories of the detected and tracked humans in the shop floor
- Lightweight statistics about the humans in the shop floor (e.g. how many people lay in each space)

Related Tasks

- Task 1.4: Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM)
- Task 3.3: Context-Aware Incident Detection Engine to Increase Worker's Comfort

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Physical Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Each camera will be connected with a system able to detect and track humans. This system will provide all the necessary information to the middleware through TCP/IP connection (either wired or wireless).

Sub-component Name

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Thermal Sensor Network

Description

This subcomponent is responsible for providing the system privacy preserving information from thermal cameras/sensors to the system. This information will be mainly focused on the analysis of the human movements and actions in the shop floor, as well as to the detection of reactive incidents, such as sudden increase of temperature.

Services

- Acquisition of human movements/actions in the shop floor

Dependencies

- Middleware
- Incident detection tool

Inputs needed

- No input needed

Outputs provided

- Trace of the detected humans in the shop floor
- Trajectories of the detected and tracked humans in the shop floor
- Lightweight statistics about the humans in the shop floor (e.g. how many people lay in each space)

Related Tasks

- Task 1.4: Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM)
- Task 3.3: Context-Aware Incident Detection Engine to Increase Worker's Comfort

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Physical Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Each camera will be connected with a system able to detect and track humans. This system will provide all the necessary information to the middleware through TCP/IP connection (either wired or wireless).

Sub-component Name

Middleware Core

Description

This component is heart to middleware functionality and provides an abstraction layer for transparent and location independent communication between different middleware services. The services and device manager makes registration into middleware to be part of middleware overlay network.

Services

- Service registration
- HTTP Tunnelling for location independent access
- Discovery of middleware services

Dependencies

- Event Manager
- Device Managers

Inputs needed

- SatisFactory tools
- Domain Model
- Device Registration Document

Outputs provided

- Output is a registration document that is used by the Device manager and Event Manager to access other Middleware services

Related Tasks

- T4.4: Development of intelligent notification and control middleware

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

[REST API for service registration and discovery](#)

[HTTP API for tunnelling](#)

Sub-component Name

Device Manager

Description

The Device Manager provides the instruments to simplify heterogeneous physical devices virtualization through common interfaces. These devices have different capabilities, communication technologies and features. A device virtualization is needed to help the seamless integration of these devices with other SatisFactory components and features (e.g. DSS systems, Semantic Context Manager, etc.).

Services

- Location information
- Geo-fencing events
- Other services

Dependencies

- Semantic Knowledge Management Components
- Other Middleware sub-components

Inputs needed

- Device related information (communication technology, access methods)
- Device APIs

Outputs provided

- Device abstraction reference model
- Virtual instances of available/DM compliant devices in the shop floor
- Events and/or Services and/or Memory maps of available/DM compliant devices
- Unique addressability of available/DM compliant devices

Related Tasks

- T4.4: Development of intelligent notification and control middleware
- T4.5: Integration of social collaboration and sensing environments for enhancing collective awareness

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Set of REST APIs which allow to retrieve the list of the devices abstracted and to interact with them.

Sub-component Name

Event Manager

Description

This component provides publish-subscribe based notification mechanism to other SatisFactory components and services. Mainly the data captured from smart and other sensor types are collected, processed and stored in a repository through the Event Manager.

Services

- Real Time diagnostic
- Contextualization of raw data
- Incident related dynamic and persistent data

Dependencies

- Device Managers
- SatisFactory Repository
- Semantic Context Manager

Inputs needed

- SatisFactory tools
- Domain (Shop floor) Model
- Interfaces for Smart Sensor Network
- Interaction with Repository

Outputs provided

- An Event type that is understandable to Device Managers, repository and other SatisFactory tools (e.g., Semantic Context Manager)

Related Tasks

- T4.4: Development of intelligent notification and control middleware

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

MQTT based protocol for notification

Sub-component Name

Ontology Manager

Description

The Ontology Manager is a tool used to manage ontologies of SatisFactory. It can be used to list ontologies of SatisFactory, to create/import new ones, to delete existing ones, to generate underlying ontological structures, etc.

Services

- Ontology Create
- Ontology Read
- Ontology Update
- Ontology Delete

Dependencies

- Integrated DSS
- Collaborative Tools
- AR In-Factory Platform
- Training Educational Platform
- Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices
- Repository
- Middleware (I/O Data)
- Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence

Inputs needed

- Ontology Models
 - Semantic models for use cases and scenarios#1 (COMAU)
 - Semantic models for use cases and scenarios#2 (SUNLIGHT)
 - Semantic models for use cases and scenarios#3 (CPERI)

Outputs provided

- SPARQL endpoint (DSS)
- Ontology network for shop floor services

Related Tasks

- Task 1.3: Use cases and scenarios
- Task 2.2: Knowledge modelling to support the human resource optimization
- Task 3.1: Semantically-enriched framework for analysis and design of dynamically evolving shop floor operations
- Task 3.3: Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort
- Task 3.5: Shop floor feedback engine and integrated Decision Support System

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

REST APIs

Software and tools (if exist)

[OSF Ontologies Management Tool](#)

[Open Semantic Framework](#)

[Protégé Ontology Editor](#)

Sub-component Name

Localization Manager

Description

The Localization Manager provides as output location information of objects and workers given as input the identifier of the associated UWB devices. This module receives either ranging or localization data from the UWB modules through the middleware. Moreover, it provides geo-fencing events when a worker approaches a forbidden area.

Services

- Location information
- Geo-fencing events

Dependencies

- Ontology Manager
- Middleware
- UWB Localization Node
- Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence

Inputs needed

- Location or ranging data from localization UWB modules through the middleware
- Shop floor indoor map
- Coordinates of UWB reference nodes
- List of forbidden areas information

Outputs provided

- UWB-based location data expressed according to relative and absolute reference systems.
- List of UWB devices deployed in the shop floor (including mobile and reference UWB devices)
- Geo-fencing event (e.g., inside the forbidden area A at time t_0)
- Data history related to location data and geo-fencing events

Related Tasks

- Task 3.1: Semantically-enriched framework for analysis and design of dynamically evolving shop floor operations
- Task 3.3: Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort
- T4.1: Development of intelligent IoT infrastructure to enable context-aware applications

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

REST APIs

Sub-component Name

Multimedia Manager

Description

The Multimedia Manager is a component responsible for handling information concerning video streams. If necessary and required, the video can propagate contextual information as metadata embedded in the video streams. Privacy preservation is also in scope of this component, where required.

Services

- Video streaming services
- Embedded metadata

Dependencies

- Ontology Manager
- Middleware

Inputs needed

- Real-time video streams from cameras
- Context-manager information to propagate relevant contextual information with the video streams

Outputs provided

- Multiple video streams
- Contextual information embedded as metadata (if needed)
- Adaptive streams based on network condition (if hostile environment is detected)

Related Tasks

- Task 2.4
- Task 3.1
- Task 3.3

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Web-Service APIs are provided to subscribers in order to receive dedicated video streams. Adaptation of video quality based on network conditions is also in scope of this component.

Sub-component Name

Gesture & Content Recognition Manager

Description

The Gesture & Content Recognition Manager is a component in charge of performing a complex set of analysis on input streams and it reacts to a certain level of configurable alerts, triggering context-aware events. The component works under the assumption that the background can be mapped and this mapping action can be performed with regular scheduling.

Services

- Gestures recognition
- Geo-fencing events

Dependencies

- Ontology Manager
- Middleware
- Multimedia Manager

Inputs needed

- Blob steams from the Multimedia Manager
- Context-manager information to propagate relevant contextual information with the frames

Outputs provided

- Gestures triggered events
- Geo-fencing events
- Historical data based on geo-fencing events
- Historical data based on gestures triggered events
- Contextual information with frames provided alongside violation of paths

Related Tasks

- Task 2.4:
- Task 3.1: Semantically-enriched framework for analysis and design of dynamically evolving shop floor operations
- Task 3.3: Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

REST APIs to provide image of the background with impressed overlay of the violator path, alongside all raw data for post processing visual search purposes. The same component can also be relocated for providing privacy preserving statistics, in order to mark most crossed intersections, areas and paths.

Sub-component Name

Social Interaction and Cooperation

Description

The Social Interaction and Cooperation component provides a platform that workers can use to interact with their (remote) colleagues. It can be used to cooperate on work related issues, e.g., requesting for help for a particular problem or for sharing off-topic interests.

Services

- Means of communication
- Sharing media and text
- Storage
- Search

Dependencies

- Middleware
- possibly Localization Manager
- Adaptable user interfaces

Inputs needed

- Network connection through the middleware
- Content from users
- Possibly location information of users

Outputs provided

- Communication channels
- Platform for sharing, storing and searching for media and text

Related Tasks

- T2.3: Social interaction and gamification development to increase attractiveness
- T3.4: Intrafactory collaborative applications for work process support

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Service Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Sub-component Name

Gamified Process Support

Description

The gamified process support primarily integrates concepts that are typically known from games into work processes. Alternatively new processes can be created.

Services

- None in the sense of technical services

Dependencies

- Social interaction and cooperation
- Training educational environment
- Semantic context manager
- Gamification augmented reality
- Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices

Inputs needed

- Existing processes
- Defined targets
- Technology capabilities

Outputs provided

- Process concepts

Related Tasks

- T2.3: Social interaction and gamification development to increase attractiveness
- T3.4: Intrafactory collaborative applications for work process support

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Service Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Sub-component Name

DSS Core

Description

The DSS Core subcomponent is responsible for orchestrating all the rest of the subcomponents of the Integrated DSS component, in order to ensure that the output of each subcomponent is using the right channel and the appropriate format in order to be directed to external components and that external components can subscribe and be actually notified by the various events raised from DSS subcomponents.

Services

- Accept safety and maintenance related events from the Maintenance Toolkit and route them to components that have subscribed to them.
- Receive actionable knowledge recommendations from the shop floor Feedback engine and route them to the appropriate HMIs.
- Handle RESTful API requests and route them to the appropriate module

Dependencies

- Device Manager
- Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence
- All DSS sub-components

Inputs needed

- Corrective Maintenance events
- Safety related event triggers
- Production re-adaptation recommendations from Maintenance Toolkit
- Actionable knowledge and Recommendations from Shop Floor Feedback Engine

Outputs provided

- UI Events for AR Platform, Device Manager and other HMIs.
- Structured recommendations for actions

Related Tasks

- Task 1.3: Use cases and Scenarios
- Task 2.4: Toolkit for re-adaptation of production facilities and HR workload balancing
- Task 3.5: Shop floor feedback engine and integrated Decision Support System
- Task 5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case
- Task 5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators
- Task 6.4 VR-enabled end-users training to SatisFactory solution

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Decision Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

The use of RESTful API ensures effective communication with heterogeneous systems, making the integration process simple and independent from the underlying operating platform. Server side push content technologies will be used in order to provide near real-time alerts to connected clients for incidents and the relative recommendations.

Sub-component Name

Maintenance Procedures

Description

Maintenance Procedures followed on the shop floor represent a considerable workload for the examined actors in the use case scenarios of the SatisFactory project, as well as in use cases anticipated in industrial manufacturing factories. A Maintenance Procedure can either be of a Preventive type, which is executed in regular time or usage intervals according to instructions provided by the manufacturer of the Asset and aims to preserve an acceptable operating condition or of a Corrective type, which is executed in the case that a fault or a malfunction prevents the normal operation of the machinery. The steps followed to perform the procedures involve the usage of SatisFactory components. Maintenance Procedures are rather data input to Maintenance Toolkit or Shop Floor Feedback Engine, than a SW component that takes an input, processes it and provides some output.

Services

- Structured and well-organised maintenance procedures
- Improvement of workers every day activities and satisfaction

Dependencies

- Gesture & Content Recognition Manager
- Middleware
- DSS Core

Inputs needed

- Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices

Outputs provided

- Content for On the job training & education SW module
- Evaluation from Supervisors
- Structured Maintenance Procedures that can be used by Collaborative Tools in training or colleagues assisting each other in order to fulfil their tasks in a more efficient way.

Related Tasks

- Task 1.1 End-user and shop floor, system requirements and specifications
- Task 1.3: Use cases and Scenarios
- Task 2.4 Toolkit for re-adaptation of production facilities and HR workload balancing
- Task 2.5: Development of "on job" training/educational environment
- Task 3.3: Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort

- Task 3.4 Itrafactory collaborative application for work process support
- Task 5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case
- Task 5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators
- Task 5.5 Evaluation, Results Consolidation and Lessons learned

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Decision Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Not applicable.

Sub-component Name

Shop Floor Feedback Engine

Description

The detected incidents will be paired with the corresponding response procedures, in order to give feedback to the shop floor in terms of actionable knowledge and recommendations, in cooperation with the DSS core module.

Services

- Information on incidents from the shop floor
- Feedback to the shop floor on how to treat incidents, how to react

Dependencies

- Incident Management Tools
- Middleware
- DSS core
- Visual Analytics module

Inputs needed

- Proactive or reactive type of incidents by Incident Management Tools
- Recommendations per incident from SatisFactory Repository

Outputs provided

- Information to the DSS core
- Information to the workers at the shop floor level through Device Manager.

Related Tasks

- Task 1.3 Use cases and Scenarios
- Task 3.3 Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort
- Task 3.5 Shop floor feedback engine and integrated Decision Support System
- Task 5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case
- Task 5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators
- Task 6.4 VR-enabled end-users training to SatisFactory solution

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Decision Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

D2.1 - SatisFactory System Architecture

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RESTful APIs will provide access to information and extracted shop floor related knowledge. Server side push content technologies will be used in order to provide near real-time alerts to connected clients for incidents and the relative recommendations.

Sub-component Name

Incident Management Tools

Description

This subcomponent represents a substantial role in the everyday activities of actors involved in use case scenarios in all pilot demonstrations supporting workers' safety and comfort. The main goal of the module is the detection of proactive and reactive incidents on the shop floor. The system detects and alerts the possibility of a risky condition (proactive incident) and incidents after their occurrence (reactive) based on real-time data. In both cases, the tool performs the corresponding predefined countermeasures.

Services

- Monitoring of activities on the shop floor
- Detection of an incident (proactive & reactive)
- Enable alerts regarding the detected incident
- Enable of countermeasures related to the detected incidents

Dependencies

- Middleware
- Semantic Context Manager
- DSS-core module

Inputs needed

- Smart Sensor Network data (through middleware)
- Events from the Localization manager
- Events from the Multi-media manager
- Events from the Gesture & Content Recognition manager

Outputs provided

- Events regarding incidents (type of event, location, actors, etc.)

Related Tasks

- Task 1.4: Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM)
- Task 2.1: Reference Architecture Design & Technology Exploration
- Task 2.2: Knowledge Modelling to Support the Human Resource Optimization
- Task 3.5: Shop Floor Feedback Engine and Integrated DSS
- Task 5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case
- Task 5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Decision Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

The use of RESTful API ensures effective communication with heterogeneous systems, making the integration process simple and independent from the underlying operating platform.

Sub-component Name

Maintenance Toolkit

Description

This subcomponent represents a substantial role in the everyday activities of actors involved in use case scenarios in all pilot demonstrations. The basic responsibility of the module is to monitor and supervise in real time the production processes and diagnose possible problems, flaws or malfunctions while triggering events for activating maintenance procedures or safety mechanisms

Services

- Monitoring of maintenance in production facilities by interpreting the measurements coming from the Sensor Network or the Thermal and Optical Sensors
- Scheduling of preventive maintenance actions
- Identifying the need and organisation of corrective maintenance activities
- Enabling Condition based maintenance
- Triggering activation of safety mechanisms

Dependencies

- Operation & Maintenance procedures
- Asset-Machinery-Production Data
- DSS Core

Inputs needed

- Incident Events
- Logging from workers and supervisors
- Smart Sensor Network (mainly legacy sensors)
- Asset-Machinery-Production Model

Outputs provided

- Recommendations for balancing workload density
- Events triggering maintenance procedures need
- Events triggering activation of safety mechanisms

Related Tasks

- Task 1.3: Use cases and Scenarios
- Task 2.4: Toolkit for re-adaptation of production facilities and HR workload balancing
- Task 5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case
- Task 5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators
- Task 6.4 VR-enabled end-users training to SatisFactory solution

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Decision Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

The use of RESTful API ensures effective communication with heterogeneous systems, making the integration process simple and independent from the underlying operating platform.

Sub-component Name

Production Activities Tools

Description

This subcomponent will be responsible to check the dynamic information from production activities, so as to detect the operating status of production line. If a part of the production line is broken (has been stopped working properly) or presents underperformance, then an alarm will be sent to the integrated DSS.

Services

- Monitoring of production activities
- Analysis of the production activities

Dependencies

- Middleware
- DSS-core module

Inputs needed

- Smart sensor network data (through middleware)

Outputs provided

- Events/alarms regarding the production activities

Related Tasks

- Task 1.3: Use cases and Scenarios
- Task 3.5 Shop floor feedback engine and integrated Decision Support System
- Task 5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case
- Task 5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Decision Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

The use of RESTful API ensures effective communication with heterogeneous systems, making the integration process simple and independent from the underlying operating platform.

Sub-component Name

Real-time Analytics Module

Description

The real-time analytics module is responsible for correlating, combining and analysing heterogeneous data acquired from the smart sensor network in order to evaluate the shop floor and production operations, supporting comparative assessment of worker's situation and suggesting role-based actions.

Services

- Analysis of the shop floor heterogeneous information
- Evaluation of the shop floor and production operations

Dependencies

- Middleware
- DSS-core module

Inputs needed

- Smart Sensor Network data & models (through middleware)

Outputs provided

- KPIs regarding the performance of the shop floor operation
- Assessment events regarding the shop floor operation
- Assessment event regarding the production operation

Related Tasks

- Task 1.2: Models for Actors and Procedures Interconnections
- Task 1.3: Use cases and Scenarios
- Task 2.2: Knowledge Modelling to Support the Human Resource Optimization
- Task 3.5: Shop-floor Feedback Engine and Integrated DSS
- Task 4.3: Interactive Augmented Reality Services and Data Analytics Techniques
- Task 5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case
- Task 5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Decision Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

D2.1 - SatisFactory System Architecture

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The use of RESTful API ensures effective communication with heterogeneous systems, making the integration process simple and independent from the underlying operating platform.

Sub-component Name

Visual Analytics Module

Description

This subcomponent presents different state-related views of the supervised shop floor. It will provide the capability to compare and assess the situation of the workers in a visual and comprehensive way taking into account properties of human cognition, perception and sense making. It will combine, correlate and visualize large, complex and heterogeneous data providing a multi-factorial exploration in the spatio-temporal domain, assisting end-users/managers to detect patterns, templates and crucial points that are difficult detected otherwise.

Services

- Analysis of the shop floor heterogeneous information
- Evaluation of the situation of the workers
- Visualization in the spatio-temporal domain of the shop floor information

Dependencies

- Middleware
- DSS-core module

Inputs needed

- Smart Sensor Network data & models (through middleware)

Outputs provided

- Visualizations regarding the shop floor operation
- Visualization for the evaluation of the shop floor and its operation status

Related Tasks

- Task 1.2: Models for Actors and Procedures Interconnections
- Task 1.3: Use cases and Scenarios
- Task 2.2: Knowledge Modelling to Support the Human Resource Optimization
- Task 3.5: Shop-floor Feedback Engine and Integrated DSS
- Task 5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case
- Task 5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Decision Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

The use of RESTful API ensures effective communication with heterogeneous systems, making the integration process simple and independent from the underlying operating platform. Furthermore, visualizations and interactions through a human friendly environment ensures the usability of the module in the underlying platform.

Sub-component Name

SOP & Content Data Enrichment Tools

Description

Data Enrichment Tools allow to associate specific "Semantics" to source data (e.g. 3D models, images, videos, documental data, etc.), typically linked by the description of Standard Operating Procedures (SOP). This enrichment allows to accelerate the creation of AR SOP (Augmented Reality Standard Operating Procedure) presented afterwards by the AR Presentation Tools and feeding both Training and In-Factory environments. For instance by having semantically enriched 3D models, it is possible to automatize the creation of 3D animations of components involved in a specific user activity. The final "enriched data", that maintain "just linked" the source data without changing them, can be directly saved into the SatisFactory Repository in order to be accessed both by the AR SOP Creation Tools and the AR Presentation Tools during a runtime session in the shop floor or in the training area.

Services

- Enrichment of source data (e.g. 3D model, images, etc.) by Semantics
- Storage of enriched data in a "ready-to-use" file format

Dependencies

- SatisFactory Repository

Inputs needed

- CAD data (e.g. 3D models available from use-cases by COMAU, Sunlight, CERTH)
- DCC data (e.g. images available from use-cases by COMAU, Sunlight, CERTH)
- Metadata bound to source data

Outputs provided

- Enriched data, ready to be used by AR SOP Creation tools and by AR Presentation Tools

Related Tasks

- Task 2.5: Development of "on job" training/education environment
- Task 4.3: Interactive augmented reality services and data analytics techniques

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Sub-component Name

D2.1 - SatisFactory System Architecture

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AR SOP Creation Tools

Description

The Creation Tools allow converting original Standard Operating Procedures, often described with different formalisms, in a new format, called AR SOP (Augment Reality Standard Operating Procedure) ready to be used by the AR Presentation Tools developed to support both training and operational environments. The Creation Tools provide functionalities designed to describe a new AR SOP both manually in an offline context and by an "on the job" approach. Latter is directly based on specific sensors (e.g. motion tracking systems) placed in the work and/or training areas, that can capture the operator's activity and recognize objects, components and tools.

The tools themselves support the technical actor who is in charge of the new AR SOP creation, by providing him power wizards, semantically enriched data management, UI based on a visual language and a lot of automatically generated contents (e.g. 3D animations, video clip, synthesized speech, etc.).

Services

- Augmented Reality Standard Operating Procedure creation
- Semantically enriched data management
- Storage of AR SOP ready to use with AR Presentation Tools
- Automatically generated contents management (e.g. 3D animations, video clip, etc.)

Dependencies

- SatisFactory Repository
- SOP & Content Data Enrichment Tools
- Middleware (for "on the job" version of tools only)
- Semantic Context Manager (for "on the job" version of tools only)

Inputs needed

- Semantically Enriched Data (provided by SOP & Content Data Enrichment Tools)
- Original Standard Operating Procedures (e.g. specific use-cases by COMAU, Sunlight, CERTH)
- Enriched data provided by Semantic Context Manager (for "on the job" version of the tools)

Outputs provided

- Augmented Reality Standard Operating Procedure, ready to be used by AR Presentation and Training Tools

Related Tasks

- Task 2.5: Development of "on job" training/education environment

- Task 4.3: Interactive augmented reality services and data analytics techniques

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Since Creation Tools are stand-alone desktop applications, they can communicate with the other SatisFactory modules mainly via LinkSmart.

Sub-component Name

AR SOP Presentation Tools "On the Job"

Description

The Presentation Tools provide a rich set of visualization and interaction functionalities in order to present previously prepared AR SOP directly "on the job". By using these tools, operators can follow a specific procedure step by step, obtain support for their current task and choose which kind of information and which level of detail they want about the procedure. Moreover, the tools themselves can become a "view channel" to show relevant information available at runtime from the Middleware, Integrated DSS and Event Manager modules. Key features of the Presentation Tools are: a) different target platforms support (e.g. Windows and Android); b) high scalability on physical devices (e.g. desktop pc, mobile devices, wearable devices); c) large number of presentation modes (e.g. in Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Speech only, Text only, hybrid, etc.).

Services

- Support of assembly and maintenance operations in AR for the operational environment
- Support to visualization of common or emergency indications to the operators, deriving from external modules (e.g. Integrated DSS)

Dependencies

- SatisFactory Repository
- AR SOP Creation Tools
- Middleware
- Integrated DSS
- Event Manager
- Hardware Devices Capabilities & Performances

Inputs needed

- Augmented Reality Standard Operating Procedure (AR SOP)
- Data obtained from Middleware module
- Data available from Integrated DSS and Event Managers modules

Outputs provided

- Audio/Visual information shown by implemented HMIs
- Log file for each executed procedure

Related Tasks

- Task 4.3: Interactive augmented reality services and data analytics techniques

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Since the Presentation Tools are stand-alone desktop applications and mobile apps, they can communicate with the other SatisFactory modules mainly via LinkSmart and/or its light version (for instance for mobile devices).

Sub-component Name

AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework

Description

The Presentation Tools provide a rich set of visualization and interaction functionalities in order to present previously prepared AR SOP in a Simulated Framework. By using these tools, operators can follow a specific procedure step by step, obtain support for their current task and choose which kind of information and which level of detail they want about the procedure. Moreover, the tools themselves can become a “view channel” to show relevant information available at runtime from the Middleware, Integrated DSS and Event Manager modules. Key features of these tools are: a) different target platforms support (e.g. Windows and Android SO); b) high scalability on physical devices (e.g. desktop pc, mobile devices, wearable devices); c) large number of presentation modes (e.g. in Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Speech only, Text only, hybrid, etc.).

Services

- Support of assembly and maintenance operations in AR for the operational environment

Dependencies

- SatisFactory Repository
- AR SOP Creation Tools
- Middleware
- Integrated DSS
- Event Manager
- Hardware Devices Capabilities & Performances

Inputs needed

- Augmented Reality Standard Operating Procedure (AR SOP)
- Data obtained from Middleware module
- Data available from Integrated DSS and Event Managers modules

Outputs provided

- Audio/Visual information shown by implemented HMIs
- Log file for each executed procedure

Related Tasks

- Task 4.3: Interactive augmented reality services and data analytics techniques

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Since Presentation Tools are stand-alone desktop applications and mobile apps, they can communicate with the other SatisFactory modules mainly via LinkSmart and/or its lite version (for instance for mobile devices).

Sub-component Name

Incident Related Dynamic & Persistent Data

Description

This subcomponent refers to models for the data related to incidents in the shop floor. The data will contain both static (e.g. building geometry, etc.) and dynamic information (e.g. human movements, etc.) of the shop floor and the incident that happened or may happen.

Services

- Semantically enriched definition of structure and organisation of data in the repository

Dependencies

- Almost all components of the SatisFactory system

Inputs needed

- Events and data from the integrated DSS (mainly from the incident detection tool)

Outputs provided

Not applicable

Related Tasks

- Task 3.1 Semantically enriched framework for analysis and design of dynamically evolving shop floor operations
- Task 3.3 Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort
- Task 4.1 Development of intelligent IoT infrastructure to enable context-aware applications
- Task 4.3 Interactive augmented reality services and data analytics techniques
- Task 4.4 Development of intelligent notification and control middleware

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

SPARQL endpoint for querying model

Sub-component Name

Asset-Machinery-Production Data

Description

This subcomponent refers to data related to assets, machinery and production. The data will be grouped following the hierarchy of the machinery components, subcomponents and topology, as well as the associations with the production activities.

Services

- Semantically enriched definition of structure and organisation of data in the repository

Dependencies

- Almost all components of the SatisFactory system

Inputs needed

- Smart Sensor Network (through middleware)

Outputs provided

Not applicable

Related Tasks

- Task 3.1 Semantically enriched framework for analysis and design of dynamically evolving shop floor operations
- Task 3.3 Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort
- Task 4.1 Development of intelligent IoT infrastructure to enable context-aware applications
- Task 4.3 Interactive augmented reality services and data analytics techniques
- Task 4.4 Development of intelligent notification and control middleware

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

SPARQL endpoint for querying model

Sub-component Name

Asset-Machinery-Production Models

Description

This subcomponent refers to models for the data related to assets, machinery and production. The data will be grouped following the hierarchy of the machinery components, subcomponents and topology, as well as the associations with the production activities.

Services

- Semantically enriched definition of structure and organisation of data in the repository

Dependencies

- Maintenance Toolkit
- Production Activities Tools
- Real-time Analytics

Inputs needed

Not applicable

Outputs provided

Not applicable

Related Tasks

- Task 3.1 Semantically enriched framework for analysis and design of dynamically evolving shop floor operations
- Task 3.3 Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort
- Task 4.1 Development of intelligent IoT infrastructure to enable context-aware applications
- Task 4.3 Interactive augmented reality services and data analytics techniques
- Task 4.4 Development of intelligent notification and control middleware

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Facility Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

SPARQL endpoint for querying model

Sub-component Name

Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence

Description

It is responsible for providing real-time diagnostics and control actions to the operators at nominal conditions of shop floor operation. The platform communicates directly with the middleware component and the DSS system in order to derive the optimum actions based on the current state of the machines and the worker's behaviour. It is responsible for providing an overview of KPIs, personalized notes and tasks that are adjusted per worker. Additionally AR platform will integrate and present the Semantic Context and the Collaborative tools through an easy to use and intuitive interface.

Services

- Providing real-time diagnostics
- Providing real-time control actions
- Overview of KPIs, personalized notes and tasks that are adjusted per worker

Dependencies

- Semantic Context Manager
- Middleware
- Integrated DSS
- Collaborative Tools
- CIDEM

Inputs needed

- Smart sensor network data & models (through middleware)
- Semantic information from the Semantic context manager
- Events and actions from the Integrated DSS
- Information from the Collaborative tools
- Information from the AR in-factory platform

Outputs provided

- Real-time diagnostics and control actions
- Overview of the KPIs
- Personalized notes and tasks that are adjusted per worker
- Presentation of semantic context through intuitive interfaces
- Presentation of collaborative tools through intuitive interfaces

Related Tasks

D2.1 - SatisFactory System Architecture

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- Task 1.3: Use cases and Scenarios
- Task 1.4: Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM)
- Task 2.2: Knowledge Modelling to Support the Human Resource Optimization
- Task 3.3: Context-Aware Incident Detection Engine to Increase Worker's Comfort
- Task 3.5: Shop-Floor Feedback Engine and Integrated DSS
- Task 4.1: Development of Intelligent IoT Infrastructure to Enable Context-Aware Applications
- Task 4.3: Interactive Augmented Reality Services and Data Analytics Techniques
- Task 4.4: Development of Intelligent Notification and Control Middleware
- Task 5.1: Preparation and Component Integration to Shop Floor
- Task 5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case
- Task 5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Service Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

The use of RESTful API ensures effective communication with heterogeneous systems, making the integration process simple and independent from the underlying operating platform.

Sub-component Name

On the job Training & Educational Tools

Description

The Training & Educational Tools provide a further specialization on AR SOP Presentation Tools in order to include the typical human interaction between the actors involved in a training and educational session (e.g. teacher-trainee, supervisor-worker, experienced-beginner). The tools allow training "on the job" and can manage both manufacturing and maintenance procedures. Training tools make use of all functionalities already implemented in the AR In-Factory Platform Tools, both for the creation and for the presentation of the procedures. Moreover training tools take more closely in account specific scenarios and role based environments.

Services

- Delivering "on the job" training and education functionalities
- Support to a bidirectional flow of data and information between different actors (e.g. supervisor-worker, experienced-beginner)
- Scenario and role based environment management

Dependencies

- SatisFactory Repository
- AR SOP Creation Tools
- AR SOP Presentation Tools
- Middleware
- Integrated DSS
- Event Manager
- Semantic Context Manager
- Hardware Devices Capabilities & Performances

Inputs needed

- Augmented Reality Standard Operating Procedure (AR SOP)
- Scenario and role based environment description
- Data obtained from Middleware module
- Data available from Integrated DSS and Event Managers modules

Outputs provided

- Visual information shown by implemented HMI
- Log file for each work and/or training session

Related Tasks

D2.1 - SatisFactory System Architecture

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- Task 2.5: Development of “on job” training/education environment
- Task 4.3: Interactive augmented reality services and data analytics techniques

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Service Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Since Training Tools are stand-alone desktop applications and mobile apps, they can communicate with the other SatisFactory modules mainly via LinkSmart and/or its lite version (for instance for mobile devices).

Sub-component Name

Training in Manufacturing Procedures for Maintenance

Description

This subcomponent plays a critical role in the improvement of the satisfaction of workers. In all Manufacturing Procedures addressing the necessity for maintenance of physical assets is essential. To do so, well-trained workers are needed. This subcomponent works using collaboratively the tools developed, focusing on the use of HMIs and AR devices.

Services

- Training in Maintenance
- Improvement of workers skills and satisfaction

Dependencies

- On the job training & education SW module
- Middleware
- Integrated DSS
- Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices

Inputs needed

- Gesture & Content Recognition Manager
- Collaborative Tools
- Gamification Augmented Reality

Outputs provided

- Data on the Repository
- Evaluation from workers

Related Tasks

- Task 1.3: Use cases and Scenarios
- Task 2.3: Social interaction and gamification development to increase attractiveness
- Task 2.5: Development of "on job" training/educational environment
- Task 3.3: Context-aware incident detection engine to increase worker's comfort
- Task 5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case
- Task 5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators
- Task 6.4 VR-enabled end-users training to SatisFactory solution

SatisFactory Platform Layer

D2.1 - SatisFactory System Architecture

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- Service Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

Not applicable.

Sub-component Name

Adaptable user interfaces and interaction techniques

Description

This component provides the user interfaces and interaction techniques that are used by workers to access the SatisFactory tools. The user interfaces adapt to the workers' capabilities and context. Novel interfaces and interaction techniques are explored.

Services

- Adaptable user interfaces
- Interaction techniques

Dependencies

- Social interaction and cooperation
- Gamified Process Support
- Semantic context manager
- Gamification augmented reality
- Glasses HMI

Inputs needed

- SatisFactory tools
- Recognized contexts
- Interaction hardware
- Interaction input from workers

Outputs provided

- Output from SatisFactory tools that is understandable to workers

Related Tasks

T3.2: Situated interaction with ambient information

SatisFactory Platform Layer

- Attractive UI Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

NA

Sub-component Name

Glasses HMI

Description

This subcomponent belongs to the main component of Multi-modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices. Together with other HMI devices of different nature, HMI glasses on one side enable Augmented Realism (AR) services both to real (AR) and virtual environments (VR) for a richer experience. The relative AR platform feeds with augmented information services both the Training Educational Environment and the Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence

Services

Augmented Reality information feeds to Training Educational Environment and the Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence

Dependencies

- AR In-factory platform

Inputs needed

- Data to be deployed coming from SatisFactory components such as Integrated DSS and sensors through the Middleware and Event Manager
- Events coming from SatisFactory components (e.g., AR-In Factory Platform⁴, Gesture & Content Recognition Manager). Some events might be audio data
- Position data from the Localization Manager

Outputs provided

- Augmented info overlaid on operators' field of view: guidance and instruction
- Video streaming and audio or images to SatisFactory components (e.g., AR-In Factory Platform, Gesture & Recognition Manager)

Related Tasks

- Task 2.3 Social interaction and gamification development to increase attractiveness
- Task 4.1 Development of intelligent IoT infrastructure to enable context-aware applications
- Task 4.2 Hardware development for context-aware HMIs (main reference task)
- Task 4.3 Interactive augmented reality services and data analytics techniques
- Task 4.5 Integration of social collaboration and sensing environments for enhancing collective awareness

SatisFactory Platform Layer

⁴ For example by using predefined markers.

- Attractive UI Layer

Type of exposed APIs (if exists)

The physical interface might be Wi-Fi or Bluetooth Low Energy